

SHIPPING SPILLS AND PLASTIC POLLUTION: A Review of Maritime Governance in the North Sea

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Foreword

This study presents the Research Project carried out for the Master of Science Environment and Resource Management at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, and for the purposes of the European research project CLAIM, which focuses on marine litter clean-up technologies. The project was conducted at the Institute for Environmental Studies (IVM), within the specialisation of Ecosystems Services and Biodiversity. The aim of this research was to gain insights into the issue of plastic pollution due to container loss and to improve our understanding of the systems and processes in place in the North Sea. Despite the limitations of this study, I hope the recommendations stemming out of the findings, if implemented, will help ensure the protection of our oceans from marine litter. This work would not have been possible without the support of my supervisors and the continuous guidance provided by Sofia Frantzi, Pieter van Beukering, and the CLAIM team. I would also like to thank all the participants, who, despite leading busy lives and the constraints of the Covid-19 pandemic, took the time to greatly contribute to this research. I am also grateful for the support of my family, friends and colleagues throughout this eventful year.

Abstract

Shaped in many forms of consumer-packaged goods, synthetic polymers, known as plastics, have become a predominant material in modern society. While the benefits that plastic has provided society are evident, its over-production and accumulation during the last century have raised concerns for marine ecosystems, maritime industries and human health. Oceans facilitate more than 90% of global trade of goods, particularly via one of the busiest routes in the North Sea, which includes the largest port in the world, the Port of Rotterdam in the Netherlands. An average of 1,382 containers are reported to be lost at sea each year, amounting to approximately 13,820 tonnes of plastic debris. Fragmented jurisdiction, frail and uncoordinated policies, can aid the shipping sector in deflecting responsibility. North Sea States raised concerns on the effects of discharge of harmful substances and dumping at sea during the first of the North Sea Conferences, which led to the adoption of the Precautionary Principle, the Ecosystem Approach and the Polluter Pays Principle. This study reviews the current systems and processes in place in the case of a container spill in the North Sea. It describes the existing instruments and mechanisms for ensuring accountability and evaluates to what extent the Principles of the North Sea Conferences are reflected in policy at five levels of governance. A combination of desk studies, applying a systematic literature review method, and in-depth interviews with relevant stakeholders and experts is used. It reveals several barriers to effective governance, which are grasped in a list of recommendations to ensure the protection of the North Sea against plastic pollution due to container loss.

Highlights:

- Reported shipping spills from 1917 to 2021 are analysed.
- Five levels of maritime governance in the North Sea are reviewed.
- Existing legal and policy instruments for container loss accountability are assessed.
- Eleven experts and stakeholders are interviewed.
- Complex and fragmented governance contradicts with today's shipping sector.

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Acronyms

AIS	Association for Information Systems
Bonn Agreement	Agreement for Cooperation in Dealing with Pollution of the North Sea by Oil
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CLC	International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage
CRISTAL	Contract Regarding an Interim Supplement to Tanker Liability for Oil Pollution
CPG	Consumer-packaged goods
CTU	Code of Practice for Packing of Cargo Transport Units
CSS	Code of Safe Practice for Cargo Stowage and Securing
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
ELD	Environmental Liability Directive
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
HNS	Hazardous and Noxious Substances
ICS	International Chamber of Shipping
IFC	International Finance Corporation
ILO	International Labour Organization
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IOPC	International Oil Pollution Compensation
ITOPF	International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation
LLMC	Convention on Limitation of Liability for Maritime Claims
MAIB	Marine Accident Investigation Branch
MARPOL	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MSC	Mediterranean Shipping Company
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSC	North Sea Conferences
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OSCURS	Ocean Surface CURrent Simulator
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
Paris MoU	Paris Memorandum of Understanding on Port State Control
Plan POLMAR	POLLution MARitime
PSSA	Particularly Sensitive Sea Area
RAP	Regional Action Plan
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
Rijkswaterstaat	Directorate-General for Public Works and Water Management
SDR	Special Drawing Right
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
TOVALOP	Tanker Owners Voluntary Agreement concerning Liability for Oil Pollution
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on Law of the Sea
WSC	World Shipping Council

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1 Introduction

1.1 Societal and Scientific Relevance

Synthetic polymers, known as plastics, have become a predominant material in modern society. Plastics can be shaped in different forms for a variety of consumer-packaged goods (CPG), in all kinds of sectors, including textiles, healthcare, agriculture and transport [1]. Oceans cover approximately 72% of the surface of the earth and facilitate more than 90% of global trade of goods between countries via cargo shipping [2]. One of the busiest trade routes is in the North Sea, from the Channel to the Skagerrak strait, which includes the largest port in the world, the Port of Rotterdam in the Netherlands [3].

Versatile, lightweight, solid, corrosion-resistant and inexpensive, the benefits that plastics have provided society are evident [1]. Yet, plastics' over-production and accumulation during the last century, or the "Plastic Age", has led to negative environmental and societal consequences [4][1]. In 2010, an estimated 4.8 to 12.7 million tonnes of plastic entered the oceans from waste generated on land [5]. A decade later, it was estimated that 75% of all marine litter contained plastics [1]. While global demand is rapidly increasing, plastics' biodegradability in marine conditions is significantly slower [5][6]. Contrary to polymers found in nature, it can take decades for man-made plastics to fully decompose, especially in marine waters, where weathering mechanisms are altered [7]. Plastics' impact at sea have prompted concerns over their significance for marine ecosystems, human health, and maritime industries [1].

The entanglement of wildlife in plastic litter is a visible effect of marine pollution [7]. Less visible, plastic particles, or microplastics, affect marine food chain through the contamination of prey, and consequently pose a threat to human health via consumption [8]. Ingestion of plastic debris by marine life has been detected in the North Sea and surrounding regions of the Channel and Baltic Sea. Animals affected include harbour seals, sea birds and sharks [9][10][11]. Plastics were also ingested by species considered as human foods, such as sea fishes and shrimps [12][13][14]. In the Dutch North Sea, plastic residues were measured in filter-feeding mussels and oysters [8]. On the other hand, 37% of the world population are coastal communities, for whom oceans, coastal and marine resources are of great importance [2]. In 2018, an estimated 6,200 full-time jobs were generated by the Dutch fishing industry, which has a turnover of approximately 4 billion euros [15]. Moreover, in the Netherlands, the economic value of nature recreation and tourism increased by 44 percent between 2013 and 2018, with the value of the dunes and coastal areas estimated at 2.8 billion euros [15].

Plastic contamination of our oceans may happen via rivers and canals, sewage discharge, litter from ships at sea, and shipping spills [8]. According to the World Shipping Council (WSC), an average of 1,382 containers are reported to be lost at sea each year [16]. The average weight of the contents of a container is approximately 10 tonnes [17]. Using this estimate, it is conceivable that 13,820 tonnes of CPG are falling off ships every year. Fragmented jurisdiction, frail and uncoordinated policies, can aid the shipping sector in deflecting responsibility [18]. In parallel, the melting of arctic sea ice caused by global warming can potentially widen the shipping routes and further increase traffic in the North Sea [19]. Thus, the prolific application of plastic in CPG, combined with the abovementioned potential increase in traffic, may lead to more container spills, and, consequently, an increase in plastic pollution in the North Sea. This could critically affect the provision of fisheries, aquaculture and fish stocks; heritage and cultural services, due to the disappearance of certain species; and

recreation on the coastlines [20]. Therefore, an evaluation of maritime governance in the North Sea, regarding container loss, could prove relevant.

North Sea States raised concerns on the effects of discharge of harmful substances and dumping at sea during the first of the North Sea Conferences (NSC), held in London in 1987. Under the umbrella of the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR), the current legislative instrument regulating the North Sea region, the NSC led to the adoption of several Principles, including the Precautionary Principle, the Ecosystem Approach and the Polluter Pays Principle, in national regulations, as well as within binding Conventions [21]. The societal benefits of ecosystem services has been a commonly employed concept in nature conservation policies when explaining the need for biodiversity protection and sustainable resource use [22]. Despite its popularity, the implementation of the concept into effective policy instruments and governance structures remains challenging [23]. Described as the “new millennium’s Tragedy of the Commons” by Vince and Hardesty (2018), anthropogenic marine litter has shed light on the management of the oceans [24].

1.2 Research Objectives

This thesis is part of the European research project CLAIM, funded by Horizon 2020, which focuses on marine litter clean-up technologies [25]. It aims to improve our understanding of the systems and processes in place in the case of plastic pollution due to a shipping spill in the North Sea. Furthermore, this work aims to learn from previous spill cases and examine the instruments and mechanisms to hold polluters liable, and finally, to assess whether the NSC Principles are, in fact, translated into measures. It will result in a policy brief with recommendations stemming out of the research.

1.3 Research Questions

This work aims to answer the research question: How effective are the current systems and processes in the North Sea in addressing marine litter due to container loss?

The research question can be further explored via two sub-questions:

- What are the existing instruments and mechanisms for ensuring accountability?
- To what extent are the NSC Principles reflected in policy at all levels of governance?

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Precautionary Principle

The Precautionary Principle was one of the first Principle adopted by the North Sea States [21]. The Principle enables decision-makers to take preventive measures when scientific evidence is uncertain and when there are reasonable grounds for concern from anthropogenic activities. The Principle aims to protect the marine environment by anticipating long term damage and by facilitating instruments to conserve and manage vulnerable ecosystems [26].

2.2 Ecosystem Approach

The Ecosystem Approach is the primary framework of action under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) [27]. It promotes conservation and the sustainable use of resources in an equitable way through the management of human activities. The OSPAR Commission mainly focuses on four elements within the CBD framework: raising awareness of the Ecosystem Approach, the monitoring of the marine environment, the formulation of policy and assessments, and the evaluation of human activities' impact on humans and marine life [28]. In 2002, the NSC revised the Ecosystem Approach framework and pledged to implement it within the national regulations [21].

2.3 Polluter Pays Principle

Introduced by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 1992, the Polluter Pays Principle is an economic principle for distributing the “costs of pollution prevention and control measures”. It states that when pollution is emitted, the polluter should bear all the costs for the prevention and control of emissions to protect the environment [29]. Recognised by the NSC in 1984 and included in the 1992 OSPAR Convention, the Polluter Pays Principle can be enforced by means of command-and-control or applied via market-based mechanisms [30]. The Principle is an economic principle as opposed to a legal principle, polluters are therefore not bounded by law [31]. Member States are required to adopt the Polluter Pays Principle in their national laws [30].

2.4 Accountability Regimes

In “Accountability and Institutional Design: Some Thoughts on the Grammar of Governance”, Mashaw developed a framework (Table 1) for addressing the issue of accountability. Six linked questions-answers were defined as a based to what Mashaw referred to as “Accountability Regimes”. These questions can clarify any accountability relationship by specifying six aspects: “*who* is liable or accountable *to whom*; *what* they are liable to be called to account for; *through what processes* accountability is to assured; *by what standards* the putatively accountable behaviour is to be judged; and, what the potential *effects* are of finding that those standards have been breached”. The answers of these questions create a framework to assess the capacity of a regime [32].

Table 1. Accountability regimes

Who?	Who is liable?
To whom?	To whom are they accountable?
About what?	What are they liable to be called to account for?
Through what processes?	Through what processes accountability is to be assured?
How?	By what standards the accountable behaviour is to be judged?
With what effects?	What are the potential effects of finding that those standards have been breached?

Source: Mashaw (2006).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 is inspired by the above-mentioned NSC Principles and the six guiding questions found in Mashaw's work. It visualises two linkages under the common objective of the NSC Principles: the protection of the North Sea from pollution. The first linkage summarises the three main elements addressed in this research: the response (to a

spill) aims to resolve the conflict (between the plaintiff and the defendant), and the evaluation of these two elements will result in recommendations.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework. Source: own figure by author.

The second linkage unpacks the first linkage. The response is studied via, first, the examination of previous worldwide spill casualties, using the adapted and further developed Accountability Regime (Table 2). These mechanisms are compared with current systems and processes in the North Sea in the event of container loss, at five levels of governance; thereby assessing whether the regime in place is efficiently leading to conflict resolution. Lessons learned, together with the findings from the research, lead to potential recommendations for the protection and management of the North Sea.

Table 2. North Sea accountability regime

1.	Who? Who is liable? <i>Who is the defendant?</i>
2.	To whom? To whom are they accountable? <i>Who is the plaintiff?</i>
3.	About what? What are they liable to be called to account for? <i>What type of damage is the defendant accused of?</i>
4.	Through what processes? Through what processes accountability is to be assured? <i>Through what processes is the defendant held to account?</i>
5.	How? By what standards the accountable behaviour is to be judged? <i>By what standards is the shipping spill case judged?</i>
6.	With what effects? What are the potential effects of finding that those standards have been breached? <i>What are the outcomes of the shipping spill case?</i>

Source: own adaptation by author.

3 Methods and Materials

To describe and review the systems and processes in the North Sea when a container is lost overboard, this research used a mixed research methodology. First, a desk-based analysis was performed of scientific peer-reviewed literature, grey literature, and newspaper archives, applying a systematic literature review method. Second, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with relevant stakeholders and non-stakeholders.

An extensive worldwide casualty list from 1917 to 2021 (Appendix A) was made to better understand current mechanisms. Based on a systematic literature review method, the protocol consisted of a combined inclusion and exclusion parameters. Inclusion parameters were: shipping spills that resulted in spillage at sea, including rivers, port and harbours, providing the spills affected sea waters. Exclusion parameters were: leisure or cruise ships, and spills due to a deliberate discharge or due to an act of war or terrorism. Hundreds of reported spills were reviewed and analysed by cross-referencing multiple sources from renowned institutions with authority on maritime pollution, namely, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Cedre, International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation (ITOPF) [17][33][34]. The exact location of the spills that applied to the parameters was reaffirmed using Google dynamic map [35].

The spills were listed chronologically per regions, and only the spills with a known month, year and location were included. A principal division was made between “North Sea and Surrounding Areas” and “Other Areas”, which are areas located further away from the North Sea, and therefore not considered a direct threat in the case of a shipping spill. “North Sea and Surrounding Areas” included the North Sea, the Channel, the Celtic Sea and the Bay of Biscay, the Kattegat and Øresund straits, and the Baltic Sea. “Other Areas” included the Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, the rest of the North Atlantic Ocean, the South Atlantic Ocean, the Indian Ocean, and the Pacific Ocean. Also, two main distinctions were made on the types of spills: 1) oil, which is generally transported on purpose-built ships (tankers), and is depicted with a white background; and 2) containers, which are depicted in colour. In certain cases, where oil was spilled in addition to containers, these incidents were considered a container spill since these ships were cargo ships. The contents of the containers lost were also mentioned in the list. “CPG” stands for all sorts of CPG (involving plastics), HNS stands for Hazardous and Noxious

Substances, and when information on the content spilled was not available they were named “Containers (Unknown)”. In addition, seven casualties, from the extensive list of 263 spills, were further examined (Table 3). They were chosen for their impact on modern views regarding shipping spills and the outcomes of the accountability mechanisms that were in motion. The seven cases were divided in two parts, oil spills and container spills, to highlight the main differences in response between the two types of spills. The spills were analysed according to the adapted Accountability Regime and its guiding questions, which can be found in Table 2 and in the Conceptual Framework.

Additionally, to provide an overview of the issue of container loss in the North Sea, data on the distribution of the 263 spills (Table 4) were further analysed. The analysis assessed: 1) how many of the spills occurred in the North Sea and surrounding areas; 2) how many of these were due to container ships; and 3) how many of the container ships were carrying CPG (Table 4 and 5). Also, a map was made to provide an overview of cargo ships’ traffic density along the North Sea (Figure 2). It was made using European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) Human Activities’ tool, which is based on Association for Information Systems (AIS) technology and maps by the European Maritime Safety Agency. Inclusion parameters were: route density in the North Sea region; and solely cargo vessels, excluding all other types of vessels. Furthermore, five levels of governance intersecting in North Sea were examined via a desk research method: Global, European level (EU), Regional, National and Local (Netherlands), and Private Sector and Civil Society.

For a more complete understanding of the problem, 11 interviews were conducted, audio-recorded, and transcribed. Ten of the interviews were conducted via video-conferencing and one interview was held in person. The interviews addressed accountability mechanisms, levels of governance, marine litter and, additionally, the MSC Zoe case, in the Netherlands. Two slightly different questionnaires were drafted, to adapt to the participants’ profiles (Appendix B). The interview method comprised both, a set of specific questions and open-ended questions (Appendix C). Three of the interviewees had expertise at two levels of governance. To simplify, interviewees with regional and national expertise were named “National”, since they both represent the Netherlands in regional Conventions. One interviewee with global and regional expertise was named “Global”, for a better distribution at all levels. The interviewees were: Global (1), EU (2), Regional (1), National and Local (3), Maritime Law (3), and Marine Science (1).

A qualitative analysis of the interviews was conducted using Atlas.ti software for Mac. The participants’ views on liability and the perceived obstacles to efficient governance were analysed. A codebook was created according to the approach developed by Saldaña (2013) [36]. After a preliminary reading of the transcripts, Open Coding was used as a starting point, to establish provisional analytical leads that can be further explored. Process Coding was applied to create codes gradually while going through the transcripts and selecting elements linked to the code groups. To avoid redundancy, similar codes and code groups were merged in the second cycle of coding, leading to a final number of 22 codes applicable under four code groups. A clearer visualisation of the analysis is presented in tables 6 and 7, and Figure 4.

Finally, the discussion summarised the findings in connection to the theories. It indicated the correlations, exceptions and limitations of the results. The results were interpreted, together with their potential significance in a regional and global context, and recommendations were suggested to better protect the North Sea from marine litter due to container loss (Table 8).

4 Results

4.1 Spill Cases that Reflect Current Systems

4.1.1 Oil Spills

Torrey Canyon

The Torrey Canyon oil spill (Table 3) was the world's first spill to draw the attention of the public on marine pollution from ships. On March 18, 1967, tanker Torrey Canyon was on route from Kuwait to Milford Haven, when its captain took a shortcut that drove the vessel to run aground the Cornwall coast in the Channel, releasing 119,000 tonnes of crude oil into the sea [37]. The thickest part of the slick reached the coasts of Brittany in France where it was given the name "marée noire" or "black tide" [38]. The oil killed more than 25,000 seabirds and 85% of puffins on the French coast. It caused damage to marine life, as well as affected the livelihood of local residents [39][38]. The British clean-up efforts involved the excessive use of powerful dispersants, which was more damaging than the effects of the oil [40][41]. The insufficient knowledge on the toxicity of these detergents in sea water led to the poisoning of plants, animals, and sublittoral organisms, and to spaces empty of life [41].

The affected parties faced difficulties to hold Barracuda Tanker Corporation, the owners of Torrey Canyon accountable, and to establish a court that had jurisdiction to enforce a decision. The spill affected coastal and international waters. The tanker was owned by a Bermudian company, from the American Union Oil Corporation, it was registered in the Republic of Liberia, hired by British Petroleum, and insured by P&I Clubs in Britain and the United States. Eventually, the jurisdiction issue was addressed and the proceedings were heard in London. However, common law claims were limited [42]. In 1967, existing conventions, such as the Paris Convention from 1960, the Brussels Convention from 1962 and the Vienna Convention from 1963, only covered damage made by nuclear material [40]. On the other hand, established procedures for shipping focused on claims regarding collision between two ships. Yet, these procedures only viewed two parties, the two ships, and failed to include third parties on which the damage caused by a pollution disaster is inflicted [43]. Therefore, British government sued Torrey Canyon parties for negligence and public nuisance under the constraints of common law. On November 11, 1969, the owners of Torrey Canyon were ordered to pay three million British pounds (about 54 million euros today) in compensation to the British and French governments, a sum that was not proportional to the losses incurred [42].

The main issues emerging from the Torrey Canyon incident were: who is responsible for the damage caused by the spill, and the extent and amount of liability. At the request of the British government, the Comité Maritime International and the Inter-Governmental Maritime Consultative Organisation, which later became the International Maritime Organization (IMO), considered the problems raised by Torrey Canyon and whether or not a new convention on oil pollution was needed to enable compensation for the damage and clean-up costs by Governments and injured parties [40]. The Torrey Canyon spill was the catalyst for moving the IMO into environmental and legal issues and for sparking public and scientific concern about the potential effects of contaminants in the sea [43][39]. In direct response to the spill, the ITOPF was established in 1968, to administer the voluntary compensation scheme Tanker Owners Voluntary Agreement concerning Liability for Oil Pollution (TOVALOP)[39]. Contract Regarding an Interim Supplement to Tanker Liability for Oil Pollution (CRISTAL)

was initiated to supplement TOVALOP [44]. TOVALOP was discontinued in 1997, but, ITOPF continues to provide emergency response and expertise to ship owners [39][45]. The Torrey Canyon accident also prompted the establishment of the International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage (CLC) in 1969 and the Agreement for Cooperation in Dealing with Pollution of the North Sea by Oil (Bonn Agreement) in 1969 [43][46]. The Republic of France set in motion the plan POLMAR (POLlution MARitime) in 1971, as a contingency plan in cases of accidental marine pollution [47]. The first United Nations (UN) Conference on the Environment was held in Stockholm in 1972 where a series of principles for environmental management were adopted [48]. In 1973, the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) was introduced [39].

Amoco Cadiz

On March 16, 1978, 11 years after the Torrey Canyon oil spill, tanker Amoco Cadiz (Table 3), grounded on rocks a few kilometres offshore of Brittany, France [49]. It was transporting 223,000 tonnes of crude oil from to Rotterdam when it sailed into a storm and lost steering in the western Channel [50][49]. Despite two attempts by German salvage tugboat “Pacific”, the grounding of Amoco Cadiz could not be prevented. The French government initiated the Plan POLMAR, the inter-ministerial plan drawn up after the Torrey Canyon spill. Weather conditions made it impossible to transfer the oil to other vessels, and the Navy spread 560 tonnes of second and third-generation dispersants carried by 35 ships. The type of dispersants was decided cautiously, a lesson learnt from the Torrey Canyon spill [50]. Nevertheless, the entire cargo of crude oils and 4,000 tonnes of bunker fuel were lost over the next two weeks [49]. Due to westerly wind in the opposite direction, approximately 35% of the oil spilled came ashore [51][50]. The accident resulted in one of the largest oil spills, affecting approximately 400 kilometres of coastlines in Northern Brittany [50][47].

Miscellaneous parties of several jurisdictions and claimants of more than 90 villages along the coast of Brittany - including hoteliers, fishermen, oystermen, property owners and environmentalists - and Petroleum Insurance Limited, which insured the cargo, brought lawsuits in the United States District Court, in Illinois, because Amoco’s headquarters was located in Chicago [50][52]. The Amoco parties were: the owner of the tanker Amoco Transport Company, a Liberian cooperation, and its owner Standard Oil Company [53]. Claims were also brought against Bugsier, the owner of tugboat “Pacific”, which was later exonerated, and against Spanish builder of the ship, Asterilleros Espanoles. [44]. During the investigation, the Amoco parties were deemed liable to the French parties and Petroleum Insurance Limited due to negligence regarding mechanical problems with the ship’s steering gear, for which Asterilleros Espanoles was found responsible [50][52][53]. In addition, it was found that the Amoco crew failed to receive training for emergency procedures. Thus, it was not the liability of the Amoco parties that was questioned, the main issues were to quantify the extent of indemnifications to be compensated [50].

Inconsistencies were seen between the 1.9 billion 1978 French francs in compensation asked by French parties, the assessments made by economists to quantify value of the losses, and the social costs recognised by the court [54][50]. The costs estimated by the NOAA amounted to 635-939 million 1978 French francs, less than half of the original claim by the French parties [47][55]. The District Court in Chicago, in 1988, after 10 years of litigation, recognised 252.8 million French francs against Amoco Cadiz (about 138 million euros today), plus interest rate. Several categories of claims were substantially reduced by the court for exaggeration, lack of evidence or the inability to prove a causal connection between the damage and the Amoco

parties [56]. Reports or records of clean-up costs were not always available and the accounting procedures were in some instances unclear [47]. Other categories, such as ecological damage, lost image and enjoyment were deemed unrecognisable and eliminated [56]. In their report, NOAA mentioned that one of the limitations confronted by these categories of social costs was the difficulty to predict losses when no previous studies were made to establish a baseline. Also, while the oil spill exposed nearby residents to hydrocarbons released into the air and the clean-up personnel had direct contact with petroleum during clean-up operations, contact to oil was not studied enough. Damage to human health was therefore deemed negligible [47].

The Amoco Cadiz spill was an acute test for the Plan POLMAR and the mechanisms triggered by the Torrey Canyon spill [47][44]. It highlighted the fragilities of the IMO instruments, and it led to their re-examination, and the participation of more States [44][57]. This resulted in the adoption of the 1978 MARPOL Protocol, commonly referred to as “MARPOL”, which absorbed the parent Convention 1973 MARPOL, and introduced significant adjustments and tighter controls [58]. The spill also led to the International Convention on Salvage by IMO [57]. Additional safety and pollution audits were added to the “Hague Memorandum” in 1978, which were mainly focused on the living and working conditions on ships, as required by the International Labour Organization (ILO) [59][60]. This case motivated the establishment of the Paris Memorandum of Understanding on Port State Control (Paris MoU) in 1982, which is signed by 14 European Countries and covers the safety of marine life, the prevention of pollution by ships and shipboard conditions [59]. The aftermath of the spill influenced the establishment of the International Oil Pollution Compensation (IOPC) Fund in 1992, raising the compensation limit for future oil spills, and the subsequent 2003 protocol. The lengthy legal battle between the parties involved in the Amoco Cadiz oil spill also brought to the fore the systems’ limitations in recognising ecological and social costs [57]. Contingent valuation method used for estimating ecosystem services and non-market goods was rejected as deemed unreliable. It was rejected again during the Exxon Valdez spill case in 1989, where experts argued that the non-use values should not be included in economic damage assessments [50]. This method is, however, one of the commonly used methods today for the conservation and management of natural resources, and for valuing ecosystem services [61].

MV Wakashio

On July 25, 2020, Japanese bulk carrier MV Wakashio (Table 3), owned by Nagashiki Shipping and chartered by Mitsui O.S.K. Lines (MOL), grounded on a coral reef on the south-eastern coast of Mauritius [62]. Around 1,000 tonnes of oil were leaked in ecologically sensitive lagoons that include Blue Bay Marine Park, Ile aux Aigrettes, and the Ramsar sites, and contaminated approximately 32 kilometres of shoreline [62][63]. The spill threatened mangrove forests, coral reefs and sea turtles, and the subsistence of fisheries. It was also perceived as a threat to the economy of the island, which is heavily reliant on tourism and is world-renowned for its pristine waters and biodiversity-rich marine ecosystem, especially in the affected lagoons [64]. In addition to local fishermen, several States, including France, offered assistance and mobilised resources, and organisations and specialists from all over the world were also on-site [65][64][63]. The vessel’s insurer Japan P&I Club contracted Le Floch Dépollution and PolyEco for the clean-up [63]. At the request of the Mauritius government, an expert was deployed by IMO and the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs to provide technical advice on clean-up strategies, incident management, as well as assist with the review of the national contingency plan [62]. Four sea mariners from a salvage boat have lost their lives or have gone missing, and the clean-up resulted in the deliberate scuttling of the forward section of MV Wakashio [66][65]. In addition to the loss of four sea mariners, over 50

whales and dolphins were found dead along the coast surrounding the crash site, including pregnant females and juveniles melon-headed whales, protected under the Marine Mammal Protection Act [67][68][66].

According to the 2001 CLC, to which Mauritius is party, the ship owner is liable for oil pollution from bunkers. Nonetheless, this liability can be limited by the Convention on Limitation of Liability for Maritime Claims (LLMC), a Convention based on the tonnage carried by ships that entitles owners and insurers to limit their liability for claims over a certain tonnage [69]. Mauritius being party to the LLMC Protocol 1976, the limits in a Mauritius court is limited at 13 million Special Drawing Right (SDR), which is about 15.6 million euros, even though Japan is party to LLMC Protocol 96, which has a limit of 46.5 million SDR [62]. Thus, only 1 billion yen (about 7.5 million euros) was paid in financial contribution in a joint fund between MOL and ship owner Nagashiki Shipping [70]. The accident was deemed a human error, for which the captain and deputy captain of the vessel were charged [71][70]. Concerns were expressed on the deliberate sinking of the vessel, the lack of transparency surrounding the clean-up methods, and the potential collateral damage provoked, as well as on how accountability is being ensured [67]. The spill sparked protests on the island that were joined by Mauritian diaspora and international supporters [68]. In an open-letter from August 24, 2020, Greenpeace asked the Mauritius government to assure financial compensation for future costs that will be weighing on the victims of the spill [72].

4.1.2 Container Spills

Hansa Carrier

On January 4, 1990, the Hansa Carrier (Table 3) was on route from South Korea to the United States, when it lost 21 containers in the North Pacific [17][73]. The containers were carrying a total of 80,000 pairs of Nike sneakers and other types of shoes, including hiking boots and children's shoes [17]. The loss was not reported by Hansa Carrier, and the incident was only revealed eight months later when shoes, identified by their unique Nike code, were discovered on Vancouver Island [17][73]. The drift of the Nike shoes was simulated by the OSCURS (Ocean Surface CURrent Simulator) model developed by Jim Ingraham of Alaska Fisheries Science Center to predict where the shoes would be found [17]. Vancouver Island, where the first shoes were seen and linked to the Hansa Carrier, was one of the locations predicted by the OSCURS simulator [73]. No response or claims were found in connection to the Hansa Carrier.

Ever Laurel

Two years later, on January 10, 1992, the Ever Laurel (Table 3), owned by Evergreen Marine Corporation, was transporting children's bath toys from Hong Kong to Washington, when 29,000 floating plastic toys fell overboard in the central Pacific [74][75]. Plastic turtles, ducks, frogs, and beavers, which have become known as the "Friendly Floatees", travelled through the Bering Strait and into the Arctic until the first toys were seen 10 months later off the coast of Alaska. Toys had been found in all various places, and a rubber duck even reached a beach in Massachusetts 11 years later [17][76]. The spill was not reported by the Ever Laurel and for years the identity of the ship was not revealed, until Journalist Donovan Hohn identified it as the Evergreen Ever Laurel by consulting old shipping schedules and by cross-referencing with the coordinates found using the OSCURS simulation [76][75]. Just as the Hansa Carrier spill, no response or claims were found in connection to the Ever Laurel spill. Still, these two

incidents stimulated further studies by oceanographers on ocean currents, the orbital period of a large gyre, and on the propagation of plastic pollution [17][75][73].

MSC Napoli

On January 18, 2007, MSC Napoli (Table 3), owned by Metvale Limited and insured by a P&I Club in London, encountered heavy seas while it was on passage in the Channel, causing a structural failure to the ship's hull [77][78]. A crack flooded the engine 80 kilometres south of the Lizard in Cornwall, United Kingdom [79]. The ship kept deteriorating and to prevent the vessel from breaking up or sinking, it was deliberately grounded in Lyme Bay, near Branscombe Beach in Devon [77][79]. The decision was viewed as controversial since Branscombe Beach is a World Heritage Site. The ship was carrying 41,473 tonnes of cargo, including all sorts of CPG, such as shampoo and car engines, and 1684 tonnes of HNS [79][80][17][79]. Within days, 50 tonnes of fuel oil were spilled in the area, which clearly affected sea birds, and approximately 100 containers went overboard, half of which presumably sunk, while the other half beached. Fear of toxic contamination prompted authorities to react quickly. Environmental protection measures and monitoring activities were implemented by the Environment Agency, a British non-departmental public body, and by governmental departments [79]. The clean-up took two-and-a-half years and cost about 120 million British pounds (about 139 million euros), of which about 14.7 million British pounds (about 17 million euros) were paid by owner Mediterranean Shipping Company (MSC) and insurers under the Article 1 of the LLMC [80][81].

The incident sparked worldwide interest as thousands of people were seen scavenging the beached containers, increasing the spread of debris and the efforts to collect it [79][82]. However, the theft of the items from the MSC Napoli did not lead to civil arrests or prosecutions [82]. An official investigation on the causes of the spill was conducted by the Marine Accident Investigation Branch (MAIB) in 2008, which raised questions on the vessels' structure and safety precautions. The container audit showed that the containers were 20% overweight, about 312 tonnes heavier than the declared weights. The MAIB believed that this led to reduced safety margin between the listing and the strength of the hull. Among the recommendations on safety issues, MAIB noted that the required report to classification societies under the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Regulation VI/2, which should include structural damage, cracking and weld repairs on main structural parts of a vessel, is either "not fully understood or occasionally overlooked". MAIB added that if the ship manager had disclosed the status of the defect, it may have led to an informed decision on whether or not the vessel was fit to sail [77].

Considering the findings of the investigation, the MAIB invited the WSC and the International Chamber of Shipping (ICS) to develop the joint document: "Safe Transport of Containers by Sea: Guidelines on Best Practices", which was submitted to MSC in December 2008. The Guidelines addressed the issue of container weight and included guidance to shippers for packing the containers, ensuring that their weight is verified and documented, and ensuring the weight of the packed containers is verified by marine terminals before loading. Even so, these Guidelines remained voluntary. With the support of other IMO States, including the Netherlands, the WSC and the ICS considered the proposal for a new IMO work programme. The proposal, along with another proposal submitted by Germany, led to the subsequent amendments to SOLAS regulation VI/2 [83]. The amendments required the compulsory verification of the gross mass of containers prior to packing, and the submission of the verified weight of the vessel by the shipper to his flag State and to the marine terminal [84].

MSC Zoe

On the night of January 1, 2019, Panamanian flagged containership MSC Zoe (Table 3) was traveling from Portugal to Germany through the North Sea's Southern route, when a storm caused the ship to move violently and lose containers weighing approximately 3,257 tonnes into the sea. Two of the lost containers were carrying HNS, including 280 boxes that contained mixtures of dibenzoyl peroxide and dicyclohexyl phthalate, and 467 chests with lithium-ion batteries. A variety of damaged CPG were spilled in the waters and washed ashore on the Dutch coastline and on the Dutch and German Wadden Islands [85]. Schiermonnikoog, a breeding place for birds, was littered with HDPE pellets [Interview 3]. Listed as a World Heritage Site, a Natura 2000 site, and as an IMO Particularly Sensitive Sea Area (PSSA), the Wadden Sea extends along the coasts of Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands. The accident attracted public concern on the environmental consequences in the region [85]. Civilians and organisations helped cleaning-up, since, unlike oil, macro debris could be removed without specialised equipment [Interview 7].

The accident was classified as a severe casualty as defined by the Casualty Investigation Code of the IMO and the Directive 2009/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 23, 2009, which establishes the basis of an investigation of casualties in the maritime transport sector [84][86][87]. The marine safety investigation authorities of the three states, the flag State Panama and the coastal States of Germany and the Netherlands, agreed to collaborate on the investigation, with Panama leading the investigation. In the meantime, floating and sunk containers posed a threat to the shipping route and ships were redirected to another route by a guard vessel. Vessel owner MSC was contacted by the Directorate-General for Public Works and Water Management (Rijkswaterstaat) and informed of its liability for the recovery of the lost cargo, after which MSC appointed a salvage company. Netherlands Coastguards, Rijkswaterstaat and the salvage company drew an emergency plan to recover the containers. Since the ship crew was not aware of what was being carried, it took more than 24 hours to establish the number of containers lost [85][Interview 2, Interview 10]. Kommunernes International Miljøorganisation or KIMO, an association of coastal municipalities from eight countries, including the Netherlands, organised the Fishing for Litter scheme together with fishing associations to collect marine litter for processing. However, the amount of litter from the spill exceeded the capacity of the scheme, and additional funding were asked from the Dutch authorities [Interview 3].

The spill also motivated an additional investigation by the Dutch Safety Board on the risks of the shipping routes in the Wadden Islands [86]. Calculations of metocean conditions by the research institute Deltares were combined with basin tests performed by research institute MARIN. The tests revealed that large ships incurred risks in both, the northern and southern shipping routes due to extreme ship motion, which may lead to contact with seabed [86]. Moreover, the tests suggested that this phenomenon is more likely to occur on the southern route [85]. Four measures were recommended to the States of Panama, Germany and the Netherlands on: 1) lashing systems; 2) loading and overall stability of cargo ships; 3) tools to monitor roll motions and accelerations; 4) technologies for the detection of lost containers. The Dutch Safety Board urged the Wadden Sea States to translate the findings in a proposal for the IMO international regulations; and asked the WSC and the ICS to communicate the recommendations, to draft safety requirements, and drive innovation in container ship design and transport [88].

The MSC and its insurer, paid 3.4 million euros in compensation for the damages and provided the guarantee they would pay 7 million for remediation measures, regardless of direct causal proof [89]. Still, according to a press release by Stichting Noordzee on January 2, 2021, a quarter of the debris that fell from MSC Zoe, amounting to an approximate of 800,000 kilogrammes, remains in the North Sea, requiring a clean-up operation that might not be covered by MSC [90]. This may be due to the dynamic nature of the Wadden Sea, where strong currents and sand prevented the recovery of all the containers [Interview 2]. To this day, the use of the northerly route instead of the precautionary area is a non-mandatory recommendation [3][Interview 3]. Lobbying at IMO for designed shipping route is ongoing, although, due to the pace of the IMO processes, these measures might be enforced on the long-term [Interview 3, Interview 5]. Further research is being made on the future effects of the spill on the Wadden islands' ecosystems and biodiversity, and whether the compensation paid will be sufficient to mitigate their costs [89].

Table 3. Accountability regime in seven casualty spills

	Who? Who is liable?	To whom? To whom are they accountable?	About what? What are they liable to be called to account for?	Through what processes? Through what processes accountability is to be assured?	By what standards? By what standards the accountable behaviour is to be judged?	With what effects? What are the potential effects of finding that those standards have been breached
Vessel	Who was the defendant?	Who was the plaintiff?	What type of damage is the defendant accused of?	Through what processes is the defendant held to account?	By what standards is the shipping spill case judged?	What are the outcomes of the shipping spill case?
Torrey Canyon	Barracuda Tanker Corporation, American Union Oil Corporation	British, French governments	Spillage of 119,000 tonnes of crude oil	Legal rules, United Kingdom	Impact on marine and coastal environment, livelihood of residents	Monetary compensation of about 54 million euros, deemed disproportional to the damage made; sparked public and scientific concern about the potential effects of contaminants in the sea; establishment of IMO, ITOPF, TOVALOP, CRISTAL, CLC, Bonn Agreement, Plan POLMAR, MARPOL
Amoco Cadiz	Amoco Transport Company, Standard Oil Company, Asterilleros Espanoles	French government, local authorities, private individuals	Spillage of 223,000 tonnes of crude oil and 4,000 tonnes of bunker fuel	Legal rules, United States	Impact on marine and coastal environment, livelihood of residents, recreational and non-value of the area	Monetary compensation of about 138 million euros plus annual interest rate, deemed disproportional to the damage made; adoption of MARPOL 1978 Protocol; establishment of ILO, Paris MoU, IOPC Fund; revision of Plan POLMAR; further research on contingent valuation methods
MV Wakashio	Nagashiki Shipping, Mitsui O.S.K. Lines	Mauritius government	Spillage of 1,000 tonnes of oil	Legal rules, Mauritius	Impact on marine and coastal environment, in biodiversity hotspot, livelihood of residents, national economy	Monetary compensation of about 7.5 million euros; vessel's captain and deputy captain were charged with endangering safe navigation; sparked protests over handling of the spill and the accountability process
Hansa Carrier	Bremer Vulkan	–	Spillage of 21 containers carrying 80,000 pairs of shoes	–	–	Increased interest in the effects of marine debris and coastal pollution, further research on ocean currents

Ever Laurel	Evergreen	–	Spillage of 29,000 floating plastic toys	–	–	Increased interest in the effects of marine debris and coastal pollution, further research on ocean currents
MSC Napoli	Mediterranean Shipping Company	British government	Spillage of 50 tonnes of fuel oil and about 100 containers, part of which were carrying toxic substances	Legal rules, United Kingdom	Contamination of the (World Heritage) area by harmful substances, littering of the coast, undeclared weights of the containers	Monetary compensation of about 54 million euros of the 139 million euros paid in clean-up costs; amendments to SOLAS regulation VI/2
MSC Zoe	Mediterranean Shipping Company	Dutch government	Spillage of 342 containers, of which two were carrying toxic substances	Legal rules, Netherlands	Contamination of the (World Heritage) area by harmful substances, impact on marine and coastal environment, recreational and non-value of the area	Monetary compensation of 3.4 million euros and a guarantee of 7 million euros for remediation measures; recommendations to the States of Panama, Germany and the Netherlands; lobbying for further measures in IMO; ongoing research on the future effects of the spill, and whether the compensation paid will be enough

Source: own analysis by author.

4.2 The Case of Container Loss in the North Sea

4.2.1 Shipping in the North Sea Region

The North Sea is bordered by the coastlines of the EU countries of France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, Denmark and Sweden; and the non-EU countries of Norway and the United Kingdom (England and Scotland) [91]. It is renowned for maritime trade and one of the busiest seas in the world, especially on the route from the Channel to the Skagerrak strait [3]. As shown in Figure 2, the highest density of traffic by cargo vessels in May 2021 is located on this route [92]. The most important ports in the European North Sea are the Port of Antwerp, the Port of Hamburg, the Port of Bremen-Bremerhaven, and the largest port, the Port of Rotterdam [Interview 11].

Figure 2. Route density for cargo vessels in May 2021. Source: own map by author using EMODnet Human Activities (2021).

From a total of 263 reported incidents from 1917 to 2021 (Appendix A), 35 spills took place in the North Sea (Table 4). This number amounts to 13.3% of the total number of spills, and places the North Sea in fourth position after the North Atlantic Ocean (18.6%), the Pacific Ocean (17.9%) and the area of the Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay (14.1%), as the regions that have witnessed the biggest amounts of spills during the past decade (Table 4). Moreover, 10 out of the 35 reported spills in the North Sea affected the Netherlands (Appendix A). The North Sea is not only one of the busiest seas, it is also considered a shallow sea, which is deeper in the North, and an area with strong currents, which could explain the number of incidents in the region [91][Interview 2].

Table 4. Geographic distribution of the spills per region

Regions	Number of spills	Percentage
North Atlantic Ocean	49	18,6
Pacific Ocean	47	17,9
Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay	37	14,1
North Sea	35	13,3
Indian Ocean	29	11,0
Mediterranean Sea	25	9,5
Channel	19	7,2
Baltic Sea	9	3,4
South Atlantic Ocean	6	2,3
Kattegat, Øresund	4	1,5
Black Sea	3	1,1
Total	263	100

Source: own analysis by author based on Table 9 (Appendix A).

Furthermore, 20 out of the 35 spills in the North Sea were container loss incidents (Table 5), of which five involved CPG and three of the lost containers were carrying unknown contents.

Additionally, as shown in Table 5, several spills in the North Sea affected nearby areas such as the Channel, the Skagerrak strait, and the Norwegian Sea. Also, more than 34 from the 138 container spills worldwide happened near the North Sea, with 11 cases in the Channel, four cases in the Kattegat and Øresund straits, and, further away, 12 cases in the Celtic Sea and Bay of Biscay, and seven cases in the Baltic Sea (Appendix A). This means that 39% of the total reported container loss cases since 1917 occurred in, or near, the North Sea.

Table 5. Casualty list of spills in the North Sea

Vessel		Location	Date	Type of spill
1.	Sitakund	England, Channel, North Sea	October 20, 1968	Oil
2.	Conoco Britannia	North Sea	June 24, 1973	Oil
3.	Pacific Colocotronis	North Sea	September 22, 1975	Oil
4.	Eleni V/Roseline	England, North Sea	May 6, 1978	Oil
5.	Esso Bernicia/ Sullom Voe	Scotland, Norwegian Sea, North Sea	December 30, 1978	Oil
6.	Sindbad	Netherlands, North Sea	December 10, 1979	HNS
7.	Stanislaw Dubois/ Omdurman	Netherlands, North Sea	April 2, 1980	HNS
8.	Sivand	England, North Sea	September 28, 1983	Oil
9.	Dana Optima	North Sea	January 13, 1984	HNS
10.	Mont Louis/ Olau Britannia	Belgium, North Sea	August 25, 1984	Oil, HNS
11.	Herald of Free Enterprise	Belgium, North Sea	March 6, 1987	HNS
12.	Skyron/Hel	Channel, North Sea	May 30, 1987	Oil
13.	Anna Broere/Atlantic Compass	Netherlands, North Sea	May 27, 1988	HNS
14.	Phillips Oklahoma/ Fiona	North Sea	September 17, 1989	Oil
15.	Stora Korsnäs Link I	England, North Sea	November 5, 1991	HNS
16.	Nordfrakt	Netherlands, North Sea	October 25, 1992	HNS
17.	Braer	Scotland, North Sea	January 5, 1993	Oil
18.	British Trent/ Western Winner	North Sea	June 3, 1993	Oil
19.	Borodinskoye Polye	Scotland, North Sea	November 17, 1993	Oil
20.	Sherbro	France, Netherlands, Germany, North Sea	December 8, 1993	HNS
21.	Marine Trader	Netherlands, North Sea	February 14, 1994	Containers (unknown)
22.	Maritime Lee	North Sea	February 27, 1996	Containers (unknown)
23.	Bona Fulmar/Teoalt off Dunkirk	Channel, North Sea	January 18, 1997	Oil
24.	Renne	North Sea	February 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
25.	Apus	Netherlands, North Sea	December 17, 1998	HNS
26.	Multitank Ascania	Scotland, North Sea, Norwegian Sea	March 19, 1999	HNS
27.	Tricolor/Kariba	France, North Sea, Channel	December 14, 2002	Oil, CPG
28.	P&O Nedlloyd Mondriaan	Netherlands, North Sea	February 9, 2006	CPG
29.	Statfjord A	Norway, North Sea	December 12, 2007	Oil
30.	Godafoss	Norway, Skagerrak, North Sea	February 17, 2011	Oil, HNS
31.	Flinterstar/Al Oraiq	Belgium, North Sea	October 6, 2015	Oil
32.	Bow Jubail	Netherlands, North Sea	June 23, 2018	Oil
33.	MSC Zoe	North Sea, Wadden Sea, Netherlands, Germany	January 1, 2019	CPG, HNS

34.	Francisca	Scotland, North Sea	October 31, 2020	CPG
35.	Baltic Tern	North Sea, Wadden Sea	April 7, 2021	CPG, HNS

Source: own analysis by author based on Table 9 (Appendix A).

4.2.2 Five Levels of Maritime Governance

Global Agreements

International maritime governance is generally guided by the UN and specifically IMO [Interview 3, Interview 11]. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) defines the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) of its Member States, and their respective rights, maritime boundaries, and responsibilities upon uses of the oceans [3][Interview 11]. Three categories fall under most of the IMO Conventions: “maritime safety, the prevention of marine pollution, and liability and compensation”. Member Parties’ governments have the responsibility to enforce the IMO Conventions [93]. A Convention or amendment needs the support of a majority of Member States to be adopted [93][Interview 3]. Thus, proposals, negotiations, and the development of new measures are a lengthy process [Interview 3, Interview 4].

A legal regime is determined according to the type of pollution detected [Interview 8, Interview 9]. Liability mechanisms for oil spills have changed since the Amoco Cadiz incident. A causal link between oil spilled and a vessel can now be easily established via fingerprint methods [Interview 2]. Once a causal link between the damage and the vessel is established, the accountability process is straightforward, and usually results in monetary compensation for the clean-up costs, which can include the cleaning of oiled animals, and property losses, if documentation is provided [Interview 2, Interview 8]. The CLC and the IOPC Fund ensure that adequate compensation is available to the victims of the oil spill [43][94]. These conventions provide a strict liability over the owner, at the exception of acts of terrorism, when an attack on the vessel caused the spill [Interview 8]. In cases such as the Prestige or the Erika oil spills, it was also possible to hold other entities liable, like the company who hired the ship and the classification society, because Prestige, for instance, was not deemed sea-worthy [Interview 2]. The IMO also adopted an additional regime which includes bunker oil spills from vessels, in addition to tankers [43].

Effective since December 31, 2004, the SOLAS regulation V/19 requires AIS to be fitted aboard all ships of more than 300 gross tonnage [95]. AIS enables the monitoring and tracking of ship movement and shipping traffic [3]. This system helps find the ship and its owner through the vessels register [Interview 9]. Still, as seen in the Ever Laurel case, when not reported or witnessed, containers lost overboard require further investigation to establish a causal link between the pollution and the vessel [Interview 8]. Many ships follow the same routes, and cargo casualties can be more complex than oil since they cannot be easily traced to the vessel with fingerprinting [Interview 2, Interview 9]. Containers usually carry a variety CPG and plastic is a heterogenous material [Interview 6]. For instance, the composition of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) pellets can vary due to their additives and production process [Interview 6]. Currents can also move lost containers from the place of the incident to other countries and jurisdictions, thereby further complicating the linkage with a vessel [76][Interview 8].

Concerning clean-up operations and costs, the Nairobi International Convention on the Removal of Wrecks (2007) was adopted to harmonise rules and procedures for States to remove, or have removed shipwrecks that may pose a hazard to navigation, people’s safety,

properties at sea, or the marine environment [96][Interview 5]. In principle, the owner is liable for the costs of locating and removing the ship and containers lost at sea [96]. One of the reasons for holding the owner liable is that the owner can be located via the registered ship, whereas crew members and ship operators can change in the next port [Interview 9]. If the owner does not undertake the removal of the wreck and the mitigation costs, this responsibility will be taken by the State where the spill has occurred, and legal actions might follow [Interview 5]. As a side note, and as aforementioned, under LLMC, claims over ship owners and insurers can be limited based on tonnage [69].

Furthermore, a container loss can be due to negligent blocking, bracing and lashing of cargo [97][Interview 3]. In 1972 the International Convention for Safe Containers issued uniform safety regulations and procedures for the inspection, approval and maintenance of containers, to be implemented by Member States [98]. Twenty years later, the IMO Assembly adopted the Code of Safe Practice for Cargo Stowage and Securing (CSS Code), which was later amended in 2011, to provide a global standard for the safe stowage and securing of cargoes. The CSS Code draws attention on the responsibility of the ship owners and the ship operators to ensure the vessel is suitable for its purpose. It also stresses the responsibility of the ship Master to ensure the safe conduct of the journey, as well as the supervision of the lashing and securing of the cargo [99]. In addition, the 2014 IMO/ILO/UNECE Code of Practice for Packing of Cargo Transport Units (CTU Code) was developed, as a voluntary code of practice for the handling and loading of containers for transportation by sea. It addresses the misdeclaration of containers' weight and overloading, the consideration of suitable containers for specific contents, the correct labelling of packages; and provides a guide for blocking and lashing, for load distribution, and for stacking heights and limitations [97]. On the topic of container weight, the Paris MoU requires port States controls to ensure the compliance of shipowners to the guidelines laid down by the international Conventions [59]. It is good to note that, according to these guidelines, HNS should be placed near the door for the safety of the crew and the ship itself [97][Interview 3]. Thus, these are the first containers to fall when a ship loses balance [Interview 3]. Plastics and plastic pellets are mentioned in the CTU Code Appendix in "friction factors", but not as harmful substances [97]. Yet, when in contact with marine water, plastics form biofilms that leach off different types of toxic chemicals. Among the chemicals leaked, Bisphenol A, phthalates and flame retardants, routinely used in CPG, have been proven to disrupt the endocrine system, and can potentially cause hormonal cancers and metabolic disorders [100]. Also, the leaching of plastics is harder to contain in comparison to oil, which can be contained via floating structures [Interview 4, Interview 6]. Additionally, small sized CPG, such as HDPE pellets, are practically impossible to completely remove [Interview 3].

MARPOL Annex V, which entered in force in 1988, concerns the prevention of pollution from oil, HNS, atmospheric pollution, sewage and garbage [3][101]. Annex V prohibits the release of all garbage at sea from ships, which includes plastics, and thereby addresses marine litter [102][103]. But while Annex V includes garbage discharge, it excludes discharge of plastics due to container loss. Furthermore, Annex V defines certain areas as "Special Areas" in which higher degrees of protection are required, which includes the North Sea since 1991. Special Areas need to be further protected for their oceanographical, ecological and traffic conditions [104]. Another protective tool available to Member States is the PSSA designation. Under an IMO treaty PSSA areas must be avoided via the Vessel Traffic Services [62].

Marine litter due to lost containers has only recently appeared on the global agenda [Interview 10]. The UN GloLitter Partnerships Project proposed the marking of fishing gear so it can be traced back to the vessel, and the avoidance of single-use plastics [105]. Nonetheless, the

marking of containers, also via technologies, to trace them when lost, or to facilitate their recovery, was not mentioned. To further develop MARPOL Annex V, the Food and Agriculture Organization and the Marine Environment Protection Committee adopted an Action Plan to include marine plastic litter from sea-based activities, and to meet the targets of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals 14 on the oceans. The Plan, which should be completed by 2025, inserts the proposal of a compulsory system to declare the loss of containers at sea, as well as to ascertain the number of losses [106].

European Union

The EU is party to the UNCLOS Convention [3]. Even though its Directives are binding, the EU relies on Member States to enforce the Directives in their national laws [Interview 1].

For instance, the Vessel Traffic Monitoring and Information System Directive (2002/59/EC) was adopted in 2002 to support the cooperation between the coastal stations of Member States for the reporting of lost or spotted containers at sea through the central SafeSeaNet¹ system [107]. On the other hand, to ensure the common application of MARPOL Annex V at European level, and to ensure that offences can be prosecutable in criminal law, several Directives were adopted by the EU [102]. The Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law (Directive 2008/99/EC) mandates the prosecution of States for damage to water quality, animals and plants [102]. In addition, the 2004/35/CE Environmental Liability Directive (ELD), a framework based on the Polluter Pays Principle, covers the prevention and mitigation of environmental damage caused by the discharge of HNS [108][Interview 2]. Yet again, plastics are excluded from the HNS list. Also, the ELD requires responsible parties to fund the remediation measures necessary, and to bring back nature to baseline-position. However, in practice, and as seen in the Torrey Canyon and in the Amoco Cadiz cases, this sort of regime is often challenging to apply due to lack of expertise, specifically for measuring non-values. To use the ELD and hold responsible parties liable for the damage on nature and ecosystem services, data on baseline conditions should be available to prove losses due to the plastic spill [Interview 2]. Regarding MARPOL Annex V, the Port Reception Facilities Directive (2000/59/EC) covers the collection of waste from ships visiting a port and aims to reduce ship-generated waste [109]. Moreover, the European Commission Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) qualifies the substances and objects as waste only if the holder intends or is required to discard them [110][Interview 1]. Until now, no specific legislations address accidental container loss at the EU level [Interview 1].

Furthermore, States are required to monitor the quality of the marine environment, including marine litter. Adopted in 2008, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) is a policy-instrument that can be further developed and adapted via national laws by Member States [111][Interview 1]. One of the MSFD Descriptors focuses on the monitoring of marine litter, to ensure it does not harm the marine and coastal environment. Thanks to this Descriptor, single-use plastics were identified by the Member States as one of the most commonly found materials on coasts. This data provided the basis for the ban on single-use plastics, the Single-Use Plastics Directive, which is part of the European Green Deal on climate change [112][113][Interview 1, Interview 11]. Moreover, the European Chemicals Agency, under the

¹ Operational 24 hours a day, the SafeSeaNet is an electronic exchange system for port and maritime safety, the protection of marine environment and efficient maritime traffic and transport. The SafeSeaNet network links all national SafeSeaNet systems in a central system that facilitates data exchange between Member States, and provides the Commission with relevant information.

Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation has requested the restriction of microplastics as an intentionally added material. Restricting microplastics in CPG, including cosmetics, detergents and medical applications, could reduce marine pollution [114].

Regional Agreements

To protect the North Sea, two main regional agreements were forged to unify the efforts against pollution. Started in 1972 and revised in 1992, the OSPAR Convention, under the Regional Seas Conventions by the UN Environment Programme, unified the Oslo Convention against dumping from sea-based activities, and the Paris Convention of 1974 against land-based sources of marine pollution [115][116][Interview 11]. Also, an Annex was adopted in 1998 to cover non-polluting human activities that can affect marine life. Fifteen States are party to the OSPAR Convention, including the EU North Sea countries Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, and France. Non-EU countries in the North Sea basin have their own measures, which are not subjected to the EU Directives. The measures that OSPAR States have in common are pursuant to the OSPAR Commission, the EEZs and the international regulations [Interview 11].

OSPAR requires from each Contracting Party that they ensure incidents are reported to the authorities, and that if they receive such a report they alert any other Contracting Party concerned. Annex III also reinforces the duty of the Commission to assess and list which substances are noxious, persistent and accumulative, and to draw up guidelines and procedures to prevent and eliminate pollution [116]. Nevertheless, the OSPAR Convention does not list plastics in the list of substances to consider. Secondly, the Bonn Agreement, effective since 1978, aims to protect the North Sea from accidental and illegal oil pollution. It works jointly with MARPOL and enforces the recent MARPOL Annex VI for sulphur and nitrogen oxides [117]. The revised Bonn Agreement does not mention plastics either.

In its Bergen Statement in 2010, OSPAR expressed its commitment to the Precautionary Principle and to the establishment of Marine Protected Areas [118]. In 2014, the Regional Action Plan (RAP) was developed for the prevention and management of marine litter, for the period of 2014-2021. RAP is composed of several Actions, which are divided in four themes: “Actions to prevent sea-based sources of marine litter, Actions to prevent land-based sources of marine litter, Removal Action, Education and Outreach”. Actions to prevent sea-based sources of marine litter ensure the implementation of the Port Reception Facilities Directive and assist the revision of the EU Directives. RAP also supports MARPOL Annex V by addressing ship-generated waste, the Paris MoU by prioritising port State inspections, and the North Sea Network of Investigators and Prosecutors by analysing penalties and fines issued by Contracting Parties [119]. Also, OSPAR is involved in clean-up projects such as the Fishing for Litter initiative and has developed several indicators in line with the MSFD to monitor and assess beach litter, plastic particles in biota, seabed litter and microplastics [119][Interview 3].

National and Local Governments: Close-Up on the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, hauliers are required to notify the weight of containers to the shipping line, prior to loading, and vessels have a duty to report incidents to the Human Environment and Transport Inspectorate (ILT). In addition, insurance for wreck removal is mandatory. After a spill, the ILT, and sometimes the Dutch Safety Board, carry out an investigation [120]. Dutch police, the fire brigade and the municipalities work jointly together under the Dutch Safety

Regions Act. The Act was created to extend multidisciplinary cooperation for the management of emergency crisis and disasters [121]. This Act was set in motion for the clean-up operation of the MSC Zoe incident [Interview 3].

Concerning claims and liability, the Netherlands is party to the 1910 Collision Convention and to the CLC Protocol, as well as the IFC Protocol [122]. According to Dutch law, a container loss by a vessel and the damage caused are akin to the Collision or Allision² rules [122][Interview 8]. Collision liability pursuant to the Dutch legal grounds is channelled towards the vessel's owner [Interview 8]. Moreover, the ELD could cover losses of non-values, such as nature and ecosystems. Yet, there is limited practice in the Netherlands with these types of cases [Interview 2]. As seen in the MSC Zoe incident, long-term environmental externalities were not calculated, nor compensated for [Interview 3]. Additionally, the Netherlands is party to the Nairobi Convention under the "Maritime Accident Response"; and to the LLMC. Nonetheless, in regards to the LLMC, Dutch authorities have opened the possibility of establishing a separate wreck removal fund for the removal of wrecks and cargo [122]. During the MSC Zoe case, which is considered a modern example of the Dutch accountability process, the Rijkswaterstaat collected all the claims from the affected municipalities and filed one central claim towards the insurer. This may have contributed to a rapid conflict resolution [Interview 5]. In comparison, in Denmark, claims from the State and from private individuals are brought to court separately [Interview 9].

Prior to proceedings, the Dutch State assesses whether the ship owner can pay for the remedying and the damage costs. Usually, the vessel is arrested and the P&I Club is contacted for guarantees. Under Dutch law, and according to the Arrest Convention 1952, vessel arrest or sister-vessel³ arrest can be applied when the owner is liable for a legal claim [122]. However, the P&I Clubs have a "Pay to be Paid" rule⁴. This rule can be problematic when the owner of a vessel does not have the means to pay for the claims [Interview 8]. And, while ships are required to report container loss to their flag State authority, if the incident was not witnessed, they might not come forward for fear of reprisal [Interview 8, Interview 10].

The Wadden Sea Area, which is a zone of joint governance, and as aforementioned, a PSSA, is managed by the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat [117][Interview 7]. The Secretariat generally follows the IMO guidelines and the Bonn Agreement, and supports the enforcement of the Port Reception Facilities at the Wadden Sea harbours. One of the challenges faced by the Secretariat is to communicate the degree of sensitivity of the area and why specific measures on this small part of the world should be prioritised on a global scale, by the IMO. To protect the area and the Dutch Wadden Islands, the Secretariat must reinforce its position as World Heritage Site and as a PSSA, and have agreed on common shipping and safety measures, under a trilateral policy cooperation [Interview 7].

On a provincial level, marine litter and circular economy⁵ are more than ever on the Dutch organisations' agenda [123][Interview 10]. The Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions

² The allision rule refers to any damage caused without there having been a collision.

³ A sister-vessel is another vessel, different from the one involved in the claim, registered under the same owner.

⁴ The "Pay to be Paid" rule is a rule that requires the owner of the vessel involved in the claim to first pay the plaintiff(s), to be paid by the P&I Club.

⁵ The circular economy is a restorative and regenerative economic system. It promotes the recycling and reuse of plastics, and the use of bio-based sources to avoid environmental externalities.

North Sea Commission, in cooperation with provinces such as Provincie Noord Holland, promotes and creates awareness in the North Sea region, and is also active in the policy sphere. The Action Plan 2020-2022 covers different Thematic Groups, and one of them, the Marine Resources Group, involves tackling marine litter, lobbying for more regulations to track containers, and improving policies on circular production [124].

Private Sector and Civil Society

According to NOAA, container losses are mainly due to the non-compliance to container weights, and other safety and operational measures. The shipping industry is time-pressured, which results in a disequilibrium between safety and efficiency [17]. Thus, market competitiveness pivots the balance between economy and ecology [Interview 3].

In 2019, global shipping insurer Allianz highlighted several problems on container ships, including incorrect labelling and packaging of dangerous goods and the loss of containers overboard, which accounts for one in five marine insurance claims [125]. Allianz also mentioned that a higher accumulation of risk is due to the soaring size of vessels, and their reduced manoeuvre ability [126][127]. Thanks to globalisation, consumers can now order CPG from all parts of the world and receive them at their doorstep [Interview 3]. Therefore, the size of vessels has increased to carry more containers [Interview 3, Interview 4].

In addition, sinking due to grounding is the most common cause of container loss [125]. The cost of fuel determines the vessel’s cost of operations [Interview 3]. Sudden changes in shipping routes and trajectory are often done for economic reasons, with disregard to weather conditions [17][Interview 3]. This may suggest a lack of adaption due to poor forecasting abilities of metocean conditions, and the underestimation of these conditions in decision-making [Interview 11]. A ship crew questionnaire by MARIN in 2009 (Figure 3) showed that extreme weather is seen as one of the factors for cargo loss, after lashing, poor weight distribution, inaccurate weight, and rolling or the motion ability of a ship [17]. Yet, climate change, the consequent ocean warming and acidification, and the melting of icebergs, will result in more fresh water in the oceans, which may lead to pattern changes and even more extreme weather conditions [128][Interview 6, Interview 11].

Figure 3. Listed causes for cargo loss by ship crew. Source: MARIN (2009).

Moreover, the coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has made unprecedented changes in how people live and work, characterised by remote-work and new consumer expectations through business-to-consumer e-commerce [129][130]. Online shopping of CPG has increased exponentially and the pandemic has brought to the fore the central role of ocean-shipping for their delivery [130][131]. In 2019, the global commercial shipping fleet witnessed the highest growth rate (4.1%) since 2014 [130]. This rate is expected to keep on progressing as consumer demand for CPG from emerging economies is growing [129][Interview 3]. Customers are not held responsible for the loss of a container and they have limited knowledge of the supply chain behind the product ordered, or how it is transported [Interview 10]. The loss of ordered CPG at sea does not affect their ultimate delivery to the customer. CPG will be produced and shipped again, doubling the resources needed for a single order [Interview 6].

From the perspective of the private sector, shipping's supply chain is complex, often producers are unaware of which ship will be transporting their goods, and as seen in the MSC Zoe case, the owner, the ship operator and the crew, are also often unaware of the contents of the containers [Interview 2]. The OECD Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) approach, of which all of the EU North Sea States are Members, extends the environmental responsibility of producers through three voluntary policy instruments that include: 1) the management of the post-consumption stage⁶, 2) performance standards⁷, and 3) other complementary measures such as eco-labelling [132][133]. The EPR considers the producer as the "entity with the greatest control over decisions relating to materials selection and product design", yet, it fails to extend the producer's environmental responsibility in all phases of its supply chain, namely, in the delivery phase. Thus, while the EPR can significantly lower plastic waste, it does not address the producer's responsibility to pollution from shipping, and container loss [132][Interview 11].

Nonetheless, since the 1990s, container loss incidents began to receive media and public attention [17]. Rubber ducks, washed up Nikes, and the photo of a beached whale with a littered stomach became symbols of anthropogenic waste in the oceans, which has sparked the worldwide interest of civil society [17][Interview 1, Interview 10]. Today, various organisations such as Surfrider or The Ocean Cleanup, and documentaries, including Craig Leeson's "A Plastic Ocean", aim to spread awareness on marine litter [134][135][136]. Other projects support citizen participation in policy-making. One example is the European Environment Agency (EEA) Marine LitterWatch, which has launched a citizen-science mobile application to report marine litter, and fill in data gaps for beach monitoring [137][Interview 4].

4.2.3 Perceptions on the Issue

When asked "who is responsible?" (for plastic pollution due to container loss) interviewees replied with multiple answers (Table 6). Eight responses pointed at the ship owner, of which three were from participants with maritime law expertise. This can be explained by the relatively easier task of locating ship owners, and thus, legally binding them to a claim. The ship operator was mentioned five times, in relation to lack of adherence to safety measures by

⁶ The EPR post-consumption management is the responsibility for producers to manage the end-of-life of their products, by implementing, for instance, a recovery and recycling system. Producers Responsibility Organisations can be hired by producers to facilitate and manage the EPR scheme.

⁷ The EPR performance standard can, for instance, establish the use of a percentage of recycled materials in production or require CPG to be designed for circularity.

the ship crew. The P&I Clubs and the producers were mentioned four times and with an equal distribution. Reasons discussed were the traceability of P&I Clubs, as registered entities; and the responsibility of producers in making sure their merchandise is delivered safely, and in lowering their use of single-use plastics. Three answers involved referred to consumers' responsibility in knowing where CPG come from and how they are delivered, as well as consumerism, as a general issue of modern society.

Table 6. Responsibility for container loss

Who is responsible?	Number of responses	Representation
Ship owner	8	EU (1) Regional (1) National (1) Local (1) Maritime Law (3) Marine Science (1)
Ship operator	5	EU (1) National (1) Local (1) Maritime Law (2)
P&I Clubs	4	EU (1) National (1) Maritime Law (1) Marine Science (1)
Producers	4	EU (1) National (1) Maritime Law (1) Marine Science (1)
Consumers	3	EU (1) Regional (1) National (1)
Cannot say with certainty	2	EU (1) Global (1)

Source: own qualitative analysis by author. Note: to proxy the relative importance of each response, the number of interviewees for each governance level referring to the response is given in brackets.

Twenty-two obstacles to good governance in the North Sea were mentioned in the interviews (Table 7). Four general themes were recurrent, under which the number of obstacles were: Governance (12), Private Sector (4), Civil Society (2), Research (4).

Table 7. Obstacles to current systems and processes in the North Sea

Themes	Number of interviewees
<i>Governance</i>	
1. International measures	8
2. Disaster management mechanism (clean-up process and technologies)	6
3. Accounting for non-values and externalities (baseline data	5
4. Enforcement of existing measures	6
5. Complexity of legal system and expertise	5
6. Outcomes of accountability process	3
7. Regulations on shipping routes, sensitive areas	8
8. Pace of decision-making process	5
9. Fund for plastic claims	3
10. Harmful substances list	4
11. Prevention and monitoring	5
12. Awareness, dialogue and cooperation	5
<i>Private Sector</i>	
13. Complexity of the supply chain	3
14. Transparency and labelling (contents of containers)	5
15. Ship size, design and safety	6
16. Use of plastics in CPG	4
<i>Civil Society</i>	
17. Involvement of civil society	3
18. Consumerism and societal change	5
<i>Research</i>	
19. Baseline data	1
20. Metocean conditions	4
21. Future of plastics, effects and mitigation	3
22. Climate change	4

Source: own qualitative analysis by author.

As shown in Figure 4, 62% of the obstacles addressed Governance, including, notably, the lack of international measures, and regulations on shipping routes to protect sensitive areas. 18% of the obstacles were linked to the Private Sector, to the soaring size of vessels, and the need to review their design and safety practices. Additionally, four of the participants raised the issue of poor transparency and labelling, which can prevent the ship crew from knowing what is inside a container, and ultimately challenge clean-up operations. 12% of the obstacles tackled Research. Scientific research on metocean conditions was mentioned as an important preventive tool to address global warming and the ensuing extreme weather conditions, which may potentially increase the risk of casualties. Finally, 8% of the obstacles pointed at Civil Society. Interviewees mentioned the lack of involvement of civil society and the problem of intensified consumption.

Figure 4. Value distribution of the themes. Source: own qualitative analysis by author.

5 Discussion

5.1 Summary of the Findings

Many of the challenges encountered during oil spill claims during the 1960s were mirrored in cases of container spills. They can be summarised in three parts: 1) the difficulty to attribute the damage to the defendant, and in supplying admissible evidence in court; 2) the issues faced in the enforcement of legal measures and the complexity of the legal system; and 3) the legal legitimacy of requiring compensation for the damage made to natural resources and the quantification of this damage in monetary terms.

The issue of marine litter is rising on the policy agenda. Yet, no regulations were found to address the specific case of container loss, and consequent plastic pollution, at any level of governance. While some measures may apply to container spills, international, EU and regional Conventions count on States to adapt and enforce directives via national laws. Also, the process of proposing and enforcing new measures is long and requires lobbying efforts.

In terms of responsibility, the owner and its insurer are usually the ones held accountable for a spill, since they are the easiest to track down by States. Additionally, prosecutions rarely include other parties in the supply chain, such as producers, the ship operator, or consumers. On the other hand, the “Pay to be Paid” rule can limit the liability of insurers, which can be an obstacle if the owner of the vessel is unable to pay, and can result in victims paying for the clean-up costs themselves. Also, the Wakashio case underlined the importance for States to be party to the latest Conventions, especially in terms of LLMC. Moreover, linkage between a vessel and a container spill can become particularly difficult when the spill is unreported, and when CPG are released from the containers. The heterogenous nature of plastics, and the leaching of chemicals in marine water, while also polluting, prevents the establishment of a causal link. Movements in a dynamic area can as well become an obstacle to establishing jurisdiction and to the containment of the spill due to ocean currents and gyres.

Another issue highlighted in this study is the difficulty to enforce compensation for the damage made to ecosystems and biodiversity. Losses of non-market goods, such as recreational values, are difficult to quantify and to hold polluters to account for. While contingent valuation of ecosystem services is commonly used in the Ecosystem Approach, and therefore in policy-making, it was, in many cases undermined by legal rules, suggesting an inadequacy of legal systems. Still, even if measures, such as the ELD, were enforced systematically, the system in place is anthropocentric, and the intrinsic value of nature is not accounted for. Plastics are accumulative and the task of reversing anthropogenic effects of human activities back to baseline is seemingly arduous, thus, prevention measures are necessary.

The “Special Areas” or the PSSA designation, which can be placed within the Precautionary Principle, apply ship routeing systems to avoid sensitive areas. In theory, this could mean that Mauritius could have protected its ecosystem by applying to designate its lagoons as a PSSA. However, and as seen in the MSC Zoe case, the avoidance of routes in sensitive areas is a recommendation, as opposed to a strict regulation. Additionally, a variety of protocols and codes of practice provide guidelines for the safe transport of containers, most of which are non-mandatory. Distinct guidelines concern the handling and storing of HNS, at the exception of plastics. Furthermore, several initiatives, including the Single-Use Plastics Directive and the EPR, promote the ban on single-use plastics and recycling. Still, all man-made plastics equally threaten the environment and marine life, and stopping their production is not being considered.

Increased global trade and consumption patterns, and, recently, the Covid-19 pandemic, have greatly pressured the shipping sector to keep pace. Cargo traffic density is growing exponentially, which is expected to impact the North Sea and the Dutch coasts. Market demands have resulted in grown capacity of container ships, and yet, poor application of the safety guidelines, and limited manoeuvre ability due to ships’ size. Time-pressure efficiency trumps weather conditions, which is a contributing factor to container spills.

Yet, the oceans are drastically heating due to greenhouse gases and other man-made pressures on planetary boundaries, which will have far-reaching effects on climate. In addition to the potential increase of extreme weather and currents in the North Sea due to global warming, the North Sea could potentially be affected by changes in ocean patterns in other areas. As seen in the analysis of spills, casualties in one location can affect other locations. Thus, the monitoring of metocean conditions in the North Sea may not be enough to forecast the future impacts of global warming in the area, and, therefore, prevent container loss.

5.2 Recommendations

Several recommendations to the five levels of governance can be grasped from the results of this research (Table 8). These recommendations are divided in three categories under the three NSC Principles. The recommendations aim to improve the efficiency of the systems and processes in the North Sea in addressing container spills and their consequent effects. They concern:

Table 8. Recommendations of the investigation

Precautionary Principle.

- Strict enforcement of all existing measures
- Introduction of strict homogenous measures specific to container loss
- Simplify the system in place for an agile decision-making process
- Mandatory international regulations for shipping routes
- Strict legal obligation to avoid “Special Areas” and PSSA
- Limitation on ship sizes and where they can sail
- Mandatory transparency on the ship crew and cargo contents in a public register
- Mandatory code of conduct for safety, and its revision
- Placement of mandatory tracking devices technology on containers
- Addition of plastics on the HNS lists
- Strict regulations on the use of plastics in CPG
- Development of a traceable “DNA” for each plastic used by producers
- Mandatory EPR along all phases of producers’ supply chain, including delivery
- Additional awareness programmes on consumerism and marine litter
- Review of the shipping sector’s business model and pressures implied therein
- Consider the possibility of banning the production of new plastics

Ecosystem Approach

- Monitoring of the marine environment
- Gathering of baseline data through research
- Further research on metocean conditions, beyond the North Sea
- Further research on the effects of plastics and on clean-up technologies

Polluter Pays Principle

- Implementation of a disaster management scheme to support and simplify the legal process
- Account for non-values and the intrinsic aspect of nature in policies and legal rules
- Apply stricter fines, impose sanctions or penalties for unreported spills
- Apply stricter fines, impose sanctions or penalties for container loss
- Review the LLMC and raise considerably the limitations of liability
- Develop a participatory process that is inclusive of civil society
- Implement a fund scheme, such as the IOPC, for container spills

Source: own recommendations by author based on the findings.

5.3 Limitations of the Research

This research faced a few limitations. The spills analysed were solely spills that were reported and on which information was found. The possibility of an even larger number of unreported spills remains. Due to time-constraints, the number of interviews was limited, and potentially less representative on a larger scale. Moreover, initiatives on marine litter are relatively recent, and even though they seem promising, more time is needed to assess if they will address the subject of container loss.

6 Conclusion

The objective of this research was to evaluate the current systems and processes in the North Sea and how effective they are in addressing marine litter due to container loss. This work described the instruments and mechanisms ensuring accountability and assessed the extent to which the NSC Principles are reflected in policy. While many initiatives seem promising, the existing legislations intersecting in the North Sea were found to be not particularly stringent. Moreover, the complexity and fragmentation of governance, and the slow-paced rhythm at

which new measures are implemented, contradict with today's fast-paced and globalised world, and with the cascading effects of plastics at sea. Increased human activities, and subsequent global warming, are expected to further impact the North Sea, and the world at large. These obstacles could be overcome with the enforcement and amendments of existing measures, additional measures, and further scientific research. Thus, the translation of the NSC Principles into concrete policies on container loss and a more defined accountability regime could ensure the protection of the North Sea, and the oceans, against plastic pollution.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Analysis of Worldwide Casualties

Table 9. Extensive casualty list of spills by region from 1917 to 2021

North Sea and Surrounding Areas					
<i>North Sea</i>					
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill		
1. Sitakund	England, Channel, North Sea	October 20, 1968	Oil		
2. Conoco Britannia	North Sea	June 24, 1973	Oil		
3. Pacific Colocotronis	North Sea	September 22, 1975	Oil		
4. Eleni V/Roseline	England, North Sea	May 6, 1978	Oil		
5. Esso Bernicia/ Sullom Voe	Scotland, Norwegian Sea, North Sea	December 30, 1978	Oil		
6. Sindbad	Netherlands, North Sea	December 10, 1979	HNS		
7. Stanislaw Dubois/ Omdurman	Netherlands, North Sea	April 2, 1980	HNS		
8. Sivand	England, North Sea	September 28, 1983	Oil		
9. Dana Optima	North Sea	January 13, 1984	HNS		
10. Mont Louis/ Olau Britannia	Belgium, North Sea	August 25, 1984	Oil, HNS		
11. Herald of Free Enterprise	Belgium, North Sea	March 6, 1987	HNS		
12. Skyron/Hel	Channel, North Sea	May 30, 1987	Oil		
13. Anna Broere/Atlantic Compass	Netherlands, North Sea	May 27, 1988	HNS		
14. Phillips Oklahoma/ Fiona	North Sea	September 17, 1989	Oil		
15. Stora Korsnäs Link I	England, North Sea	November 5, 1991	HNS		
16. Nordfrakt	Netherlands, North Sea	October 25, 1992	HNS		
17. Braer	Scotland, North Sea	January 5, 1993	Oil		
18. British Trent/ Western Winner	North Sea	June 3, 1993	Oil		
19. Borodinskoye Polye	Scotland, North Sea	November 17, 1993	Oil		
20. Sherbro	France, Netherlands, Germany, North Sea	December 8, 1993	HNS		
21. Marine Trader	Netherlands, North Sea	February 14, 1994	Containers (unknown)		
22. Maritime Lee	North Sea	February 27, 1996	Containers (unknown)		
23. Bona Fulmar/Teoalt off Dunkirk	Channel, North Sea	January 18, 1997	Oil		
24. Renne	North Sea	February 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)		
25. Apus	Netherlands, North Sea	December 17, 1998	HNS		
26. Multitank Ascania	Scotland, North Sea, Norwegian Sea	March 19, 1999	HNS		
27. Tricolor/Kariba	France, North Sea, Channel	December 14, 2002	Oil, CPG		
28. P&O Nedlloyd Mondriaan	Netherlands, North Sea	February 9, 2006	CPG		
29. Statfjord A	Norway, North Sea	December 12, 2007	Oil		
30. Godafoss	Norway, Skagerrak, North Sea	February 17, 2011	Oil, HNS		
31. Flinterstar/Al Oraiq	Belgium, North Sea	October 6, 2015	Oil		
32. Bow Jubail	Netherlands, North Sea	June 23, 2018	Oil		
33. MSC Zoe	North Sea, Wadden Sea, Netherlands, Germany	January 1, 2019	CPG, HNS		
34. Francisca	Scotland, North Sea	October 31, 2020	CPG		
35. Baltic Tern	North Sea, Wadden Sea	April 7, 2021	CPG, HNS		

Channel

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
36. Ocean Liberty	France, Celtic Sea, Channel	July 23, 1947	Oil, HNS
37. Allegrity	England, Channel	December 13, 1961	Oil
38. Pacific Glory	England, Channel	October 10, 1970	Oil
39. Texaco Caribbean/Paracas	Channel	January 11, 1971	Oil
40. Olympic Alliance/ Royal Navy Frigate HMS Achilles	Channel	November 12, 1975	Oil
41. Kini Kersten	France, Channel	January 1, 1987	Oil
42. Perintis	Channel	March 13, 1989	HNS
43. Rosebay/Diane Marie	England, Channel	May 12, 1990	Oil
44. Grape One	Channel	December 9, 1993	HNS
45. Ming Fortune	Channel	April (unknown), 1994	Containers (unknown)
46. Katja	France, Channel	August 7, 1997	Oil
47. Allegra	Channel	October 1, 1997	HNS
48. MSC Rosa M	France, Channel	November 30, 1997	HNS
49. Ever Decent/Norwegian Dream	England, Channel	August 28, 1999	HNS
50. Ece/General Grot Rowecki	Guernsey, Channel	January 2006	HNS
51. MSC Napoli	Channel	January 18, 2007	Oil, CPG, HNS
52. Ice Prince	Channel	January 15, 2008	Oil, CPG
53. MSC Flaminia	Channel, international waters	July 14, 2012	HNS
54. Nijptangh	France, Channel	October 15, 2015	Oil

Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
55. Foucault	France, Bay of Biscay	September 18, 1940	Oil
56. Torrey Canyon	France, England, Celtic Sea	March 18, 1967	Oil
57. Dona Marika	Wales, Celtic Sea	August 5, 1973	Oil
58. Universe Leader	Ireland, Celtic Sea	October 22, 1974	Oil
59. Afran Zodiac	Ireland, Celtic Sea	January 11, 1975	Oil
60. Olympic Bravery	France, Celtic Sea	January 24, 1976	Oil
61. Boehlen	Sein Island, Celtic Sea	October 15, 1976	Oil
62. Amoco Cadiz	France, Celtic Sea	March 16, 1978	Oil
63. Christos Bitas	Wales, Celtic Sea	October 12, 1978	Oil
64. Betelgeuse	Ireland, Celtic Sea	January 8, 1979	Oil
65. Sea Valiant	France, Celtic Sea	March 13, 1979	Oil
66. Gino/Team Castor	France, Celtic Sea	April 28, 1979	Oil
67. Peter Sif	France, Celtic Sea	November 15, 1979	Oil
68. Tanio	France, Celtic Sea	March 7, 1980	Oil
69. MV Kowloon Bridge	Ireland, Celtic Sea	November 22, 1986	Oil
70. Brea	France, Celtic Sea	January 22, 1988	HNS
71. Amazzone	France, Celtic Sea	January 30, 1988	Oil
72. Mercedes del Mar	Bay of Biscay	December 12, 1989	Containers (unknown)
73. Sea Empress	Wales, Celtic Sea	February 15, 1996	Oil
74. Albion II	France, Celtic Sea	February 18, 1997	HNS
75. Kairo	France, Bay of Biscay	December 31, 1997	HNS
76. Junior M	France, Celtic Sea	October 4, 1999	HNS
77. Erika	France, Bay of Biscay	December 12, 1999	Oil
78. Balu	France, Bay of Biscay	March 20, 2001	HNS
79. Lykes Liberator	France, Celtic Sea	February 2, 2002	CPG, HNS
80. Norrisia	France, Celtic Sea	March 4, 2002	Oil

81. Bow Eagle	Sein Island, Celtic Sea	August 26, 2002	HNS
82. Barbaros Kiran	France, Celtic Sea	October 30, 2002	Oil
83. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay	February 17, 2006	CPG
84. Rokia Delmas	France, Bay of Biscay	October 24, 2006	Oil
85. Donges Refinery	France, Loire, Bay of Biscay	March 16, 2008	Oil
86. Admiral Kuznetsov	Celtic Sea	February 14, 2009	Oil
87. YM Uranus/ Hanjin Rizhao	France, Celtic Sea	October 8, 2010	HNS
88. Union Neptune	France, Bay of Biscay	July 22, 2011	HNS
89. TK Bremen	France, Bay of Biscay	December 16, 2011	Oil
90. Luno	France, Bay of Biscay	February 5, 2014	Oil
91. Grande America	France, Bay of Biscay	March 10, 2019	Oil, CPG

Kattegat, Øresund

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
92. Poona	Sweden, Kattegat	July 15, 1971	HNS
93. René 16	Sweden, Kattegat	January 16, 1976	HNS
94. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat	March 28, 2000	HNS
95. Kemira	Sweden, Øresund	February 4, 2005	HNS

Baltic Sea

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
96. Mundogas Oslo	Gulf of Bothnia, Baltic Sea	October 22, 1966	HNS
97. Othello	Sweden, Baltic Sea	March 20, 1970	Oil
98. Amalie Essberger	Sweden, Baltic Sea	January 13, 1973	HNS
99. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat, Baltic Sea	March 28, 2000	HNS
100. Baltic Carrier/Tern	Denmark, Baltic Sea	March 29, 2001	Oil
101. Fu Shan Hai/Gdynia	Baltic Sea	May 31, 2003	Oil, HNS
102. Golden Sky	Latvia, Baltic Sea	January 15, 2007	HNS
103. Annabella	Baltic Sea	February 26, 2007	HNS
104. Linda	Sweden, Baltic Sea	February 6, 2010	HNS

Other Areas

Mediterranean Sea

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
105. Cavtat/Lady Rita	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	July 14, 1974	HNS
106. Pavlos V	Italy, Mediterranean Sea	January 11, 1978	Oil
107. Brigitta Montanari	Croatia, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	November 16, 1984	HNS
108. Ocean Spirit	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	April 15, 1988	HNS
109. Sea Spirit/Hesperus	Spain, Mediterranean Sea	August 6, 1990	Oil
110. Continental Lotus	Eastern Mediterranean Sea	January 21, 1991	HNS
111. Alessandro Primo	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	February 1, 1991	HNS
112. Haven	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	April 11, 1991	Oil
113. Scaieni	Italy, Mediterranean Sea	December 7, 1991	HNS
114. Kaptan Manolis I	Tunisia, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 10, 1996	HNS
115. Anis Rose	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 30, 1996	HNS
116. Kira	Greece, Mediterranean Sea	February 9, 1996	Oil, HNS
117. Fenes	Corsica, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 25, 1996	CPG

118. Abdul Rahman	Libya, Mediterranean Sea	November 20, 1997	Oil, CPG, HNS
119. Dogruyollar IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	February 2, 1998	HNS
120. Enalios Thetis	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	May 6, 1999	Oil
121. CMA Djakarta	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 10, 1999	HNS
122. Rofayda	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 28, 1999	Oil, CPG
123. Eurobulker IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 8, 2000	Oil, HNS
124. Castor	Morocco, Alboran Sea, Mediterranean Sea	December 31, 2000	Oil
125. Camadan	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	March 12, 2002	HNS
126. Spabunker IV	Spain, Bay of Gibraltar, Mediterranean Sea	January 21, 2003	Oil
127. MSC Al Amine	Tunisia, Mediterranean Sea	February 15, 2005	Oil
128. New Flame/Torm Gertrud	Gibraltar, Mediterranean Sea	August, 12, 2007	Oil
129. CMA CGM Strauss/Francia	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	February 19, 2010	Oil

Black Sea

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
130. Independenta/ Evrialy	Turkey, Black Sea	November 15, 1979	Oil
131. Nassia/ Shipbroker	Bosphorus strait, Black Sea	March 13, 1994	Oil
132. Kerch Strait	Black Sea	November 11, 2007	Oil, HNS

North Atlantic Ocean

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
133. Mont Blanc/Imo	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	December 6, 1917	CPG, HNS
134. Grandcamp	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	April 16, 1947	HNS
135. Janina	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 18, 1957	Oil
136. Bonifaz	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	July 3, 1964	Oil
137. Spyros Lemnos	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 1, 1968	Oil
138. Julius Schindler	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	February 11, 1969	Oil
139. Hamilton Trader/ Hannes Kuppel	Irish Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	April 30, 1969	Oil
140. Al Bacruz	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 14, 1970	Oil
141. Polycommander	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	May 5, 1970	Oil
142. Erkowit/ Durtmond	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	October 11, 1970	HNS
143. Golden Drake	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 28, 1972	Oil
144. Giuseppe Giuletti	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	April 1, 1972	Oil
145. Golar Patricia	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 5, 1973	Oil
146. Splendid Breeze	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 6, 1973	Oil
147. Jakob Maersk	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 29, 1975	Oil
148. Urquiola	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	May 12, 1976	Oil
149. Andros Patria	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 31, 1978	Oil
150. Kurdistan	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	March 15, 1979	Oil

151. Atlantic Empress/Aegean Captain	Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	July 19, 1979	Oil
152. Turgut Reis	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 15, 1979	Oil
153. Cason	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 5, 1987	HNS
154. Odyssey	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	November 10, 1988	Oil
155. Khark 5	Spain, Morocco, North Atlantic Ocean	December 19, 1989	Oil
156. Aragon	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	December 29, 1989	Oil
157. Kimya	Irish Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	January 6, 1991	HNS
158. Vistabella	Caribbean Sea, near North Atlantic Ocean	March 7, 1991	Oil
159. Santa Clara I	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	January 4, 1992	HNS
160. Hyderabad	U.S. East Coast, North Atlantic Ocean	January 24, 1992	Containers (unknown)
161. Jans	LaGuardia, North Atlantic Ocean	September 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
162. Aegean Sea	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 3, 1992	Oil
163. Cercal	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	October 2, 1994	Oil
164. MSC Claudia	Boston, North Atlantic Ocean	January (unknown), 1996	Containers (unknown)
165. Ponce Trader	New Orleans, North Atlantic Ocean	September 11, 1996	Containers (unknown)
166. Igloo Moon	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	November 6, 1996	HNS
167. Pol America	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	March 31, 1997	Containers (unknown)
168. MSC Carla	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	November 24, 1997	CPG, HNS
169. Kate Maersk	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November (unknown), 1997	Containers (unknown)
170. MSC Rita	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	December 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
171. Dolly	Martinique, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	November 5, 1999	Oil
172. Guayama	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
173. Humacao	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
174. Ming Ocean	North Atlantic	April (unknown), 2000	Containers (unknown)
175. Coral Bulker	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	December 25, 2000	Oil, CPG
176. Prestige	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 13, 2002	Oil
177. Bow Mariner	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	February 28, 2004	HNS
178. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay, North Atlantic Ocean	February 17, 2006	CPG
179. CMA CGM Verdi	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	February 18, 2006	CPG
180. Eagle Otome / Barge	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	January 23, 2010	Oil
181. Deepwater Horizon	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	April 20, 2010	Oil

South Atlantic Ocean

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
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182. Castillo de Bellver	South Africa, South Atlantic Ocean	August 6, 1983	Oil
183. ABT Summer	Angola, South Atlantic Ocean	May 28, 1991	Oil
184. San Jorge	Uruguay, South Atlantic Ocean	February 8, 1997	Oil
185. Treasure	South Africa, South Atlantic Ocean	June 26, 2000	Oil
186. Vicuña	Brazil, South Atlantic Ocean	November 15, 2004	Oil, HNS
187. Oliva	Tristan da Cunha, South Atlantic Ocean	March 16, 2011	Oil, CPG

Indian Ocean

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
188. Oceanic Grandeur	Australia, Indian Ocean	March 3, 1970	Oil
189. Sea Star	Gulf of Oman, Indian Ocean	December 19, 1972	Oil
190. Princess Anne Marie	Australia, Indian Ocean	July 14, 1975	Oil
191. Ariadne	Somalia, Indian Ocean	August 24, 1985	HNS
192. Korean Star	Australia, Indian Ocean	May 20, 1988	Oil
193. Kirki	Australia, Indian Ocean	July 21, 1991	Oil
194. Katina P	Mozambique, Indian Ocean	April 16, 1992	Oil
195. Era	Australia, Indian Ocean	August 30, 1992	Oil
196. Infiniti	Curaçao, Caribbean Sea, Indian Ocean	July 31, 1995	CPG
197. Leerort	Indian Ocean	September 19, 1998	Containers (unknown)
198. Natuna Sea	Indonesia, Indian Ocean	October 3, 2000	Oil
199. CMA CGM Normandie	Singapore Strait, Indian Ocean	March 27, 2001	CPG
200. Hanjin Pennsylvania	Indian Ocean	November 11, 2002	HNS
201. Tasman Spirit	Pakistan, Arabian Sea, Indian Ocean	July 27, 2003	Oil
202. Adamandas	Reunion Island, Indian Ocean	September 22, 2003	HNS
203. Al Samidoun	Egypt, Suez Canal, Red Sea, Indian Ocean	December 14, 2004	Oil
204. Tugen	Madagascar, Indian Ocean	February 3, 2006	Oil
205. Hyundai Fortune	Gulf of Aden, Indian Ocean	March 21, 2006	HNS
206. Bright Artemis	Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean	August 14, 2006	Oil
207. Granba	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	April 9, 2009	HNS
208. Gülser Ana	Madagascar, Indian Ocean	August 26, 2009	Oil, HNS
209. MSC Chitra/MV Khalijia II	India, Arabian Sea, Indian Ocean	August 07, 2010	Oil, HNS
210. Rak Carrier	India, Indian Ocean	August 4, 2011	Oil
211. Tycoon	Australia, Indian Ocean	January 8, 2012	Oil, HNS
212. Stolt Valor	Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean	March 16, 2012	Oil, HNS
213. MOL Comfort	Indian Ocean	June 17, 2013	Oil, HNS
214. MSC Palak	South Africa, Indian Ocean	July 14, 2020	CPG
215. MV Wakashio	Mauritius, Indian Ocean	July 25, 2020	Oil
216. X-Press Pearl	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	May 27, 2021	Oil, CPG, HNS

Pacific Ocean

Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
217. Sygna	Australia, South Pacific Ocean	May 26, 1974	Oil
218. Yuyo Maru N°10/Pacific Alice	Japan, North Pacific Ocean	November 9, 1974	HNS

219. Lindenbank	Kiribati, North Pacific Ocean	August 17, 1975	HNS
220. Irene's Challenge	North Pacific Ocean	January 18, 1977	Oil
221. Hawaiian Patriot	Honolulu, North Pacific Ocean	February 23, 1977	Oil
222. World Encouragement	Australia, Tasman Sea, South Pacific Ocean	September 10, 1979	Oil
223. Exxon Valdez	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean	March 24, 1989	Oil
224. Hansa Carrier	Canada, Alaska, international, North Pacific	January 4, 1990	CPG
225. Ever Laurel	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean, international	January, 10, 1992	CPG
226. Uni-Humanity	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
227. Stella 1	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 27, 1992	Containers (unknown)
228. N°1 Chung Mu/N°1 Chon Stone	China, South China Sea, North West Pacific Ocean	March 9, 1995	HNS
229. Alexandria III	South Korea, West Pacific Ocean	June 30, 1995	Containers (unknown)
230. Sea Prince	Korea, Japan, East China Sea, Sea of Japan, West Pacific Ocean	July 23, 1995	Oil
231. Nakhodka	Japan, North Pacific Ocean	January 2, 1997	Oil
232. Konemu	New Caledonia, South Pacific Ocean	January 23, 1997	Oil
233. Sealand Pacific	Pacific Ocean	January 20, 1998	Containers (unknown)
234. Koon Hong 211	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	April 21, 1998	Containers (unknown)
235. APL China	Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
236. President Adams	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
237. Ever Union	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
238. Ever Given	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
239. Union Rotoiti	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	April 26, 1999	Containers (unknown)
240. Laura d'Amato	Australia, South Pacific Ocean	August 3, 1999	Oil
241. OOCL America	Mid-Pacific Ocean	January 26, 2000	Containers (unknown)
242. Choyang Honour	Mid-Pacific Ocean	February 4, 2000	Containers (unknown)
243. Bunga Teratai Satu	Australia, Coral Sea, West Pacific Ocean	November 2, 2000	HNS
244. Jessica	Ecuador, South Pacific Ocean	January 16, 2001	Oil
245. Co-op Venture	Japan, Shibushi Bay, North Pacific Ocean	July 25, 2002	Oil, CPG
246. Selendang Ayu	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean	December 7, 2004	Oil
247. Solar 1	Philippines, West Pacific Ocean	August 11, 2006	Oil
248. Hebei Spirit/Samsung 1	South Korea, West Pacific Ocean	December 7, 2007	Oil
249. Princess of the Stars	Philippines, West Pacific Ocean	June 21, 2008	Oil, HNS
250. Pacific Adventurer	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	March 11, 2009	Oil, HNS
251. Shen Neng 1	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	April 3, 2010	Oil, HNS
252. Rena	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	October 5, 2011	Oil, HNS
253. Bareli	China, North Pacific Ocean	March 15, 2012	Oil, HNS

254. Bunga Alpinia	Malaysia, South China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	July 26, 2012	Oil
255. Asian Lily	Papua New-Guinea, South Pacific Ocean	December 24, 2012	Oil
256. CMA CGM Florida/Chou Shan	China, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	March 18, 2013	Oil
257. TS Taipei	Taiwan, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	March 10, 2016	Oil
258. MT Sanchi	China, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	January 6, 2018	Oil
259. ONE Apus	Pacific Ocean	November 30, 2020	CPG, HNS
260. MV Ever Liberal	Japan, West Pacific Ocean	December 30, 2020	CPG
261. Maersk Essen	Pacific Ocean	January 16, 2021	CPG
262. Maersk Eindhoven	Pacific Ocean	February 17, 2021	CPG
263. A Symphony/Sea Justice	China, Yellow Sea, West Pacific Ocean	April 27, 2021	Oil

Source: own analysis by author.

Appendix B: Interview Participants

Table 10. List of participants

Interview number	Name	Position	Expertise
1	Anonymous	Representative, Marine Environment and Water Industry, European Commission	EU
2	Edward Brans	Attorney in charge of the MSC Zoe lawsuit; Professor of Sustainability and Environmental Liability, Utrecht University	Maritime Law
3	Mike Mannaart	Secretary, Kommunernes International Miljøorganisation	Regional
4	Monika Peterlin	Expert Sustainability Transitions for Oceans and Freshwater, European Environment Agency	EU
5	Mareike Erfeling	Representative, OSPAR Commission; Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Rijkswaterstaat	Regional and National
6	Astrid Fischer	Research Fellow in Analytical Chemistry, School of Biological and Marine Sciences, University of Plymouth	Marine Science
7	Anonymous	Representative, Common Wadden Sea Secretariat	Local
8	Nol van Hal	Attorney on Maritime Law, Specialised in Ship Collisions, Salvage, Limitation of Liability, Shipbuilding, Ship Arrests, Marine Insurance and Offshore Contracting	Maritime Law
9	Ann Toft Kristensen	Ex-Chairwoman, North Sea Network of Investigators and Prosecutors; Senior Consultant, Danish Environmental Board of Appeal (present)	Maritime Law
10	Yolanda Schmal	Policy Advisor Circular Economy, North Sea Commission; Representative, Provincie Noord-Holland	Regional and National
11	Patrycja Enet	United Nations International Expert - UN Secretariat of the Environment Management Group, United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change Secretariat; EU MSP Expert North Sea focal point, European MSP Assistance Mechanism of the European Commission; Senior Advisor at Aktis Hydraulics.	Global and Regional

Appendix C: Interview Protocol

Table 11. Interview questionnaire 1 - *Governance measures*

- General question**
1. Can you tell me briefly about your involvement in the efforts to reduce marine litter?
- Shipping spill prevention**
2. Can you give a few examples of existing measures (e.g. technologies, initiatives, regulations), at the local, national, EU, regional and global levels to prevent risks of cargo loss by ships in the North Sea?
 3. In your opinion, are these measures sufficient?
 4. Do you think there are other types of measures that could help prevent risks of cargo loss? If yes, which?
- Shipping spill mitigation**
5. In the case of a cargo ship spill, who, in your opinion, should be liable for the potential damage, and to whom?
 6. Can you give a few examples of existing measures at the local, national, EU, regional and global levels for holding the responsible entity (or entities) to account in the event of a cargo ship spill?
 7. In your opinion, are these measures proportional to the damage made?
 8. Do you think there should be additional measures to mitigate the damage made by cargo loss? If yes, which?
- Shipping spill incidents**
9. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the legal/policy response to a plastic spill incident and other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?
- Final question – Shipping spill management**
10. Do you have any other recommendations to better protect the North Sea from plastic pollution due to cargo ship spills?
- Additional questions**
11. In your view, what are the main repercussions of a cargo ship spill incident on the environment and on society?
 12. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the effects of a plastic spill incident and the effects of other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?
 13. Would you say the responsibility in the event of a cargo loss is fairly spread? Please explain.
 14. Who, in your opinion, should assess the amount of money needed to compensate for the damage caused by a cargo ship spill, and how should this amount be calculated?
 15. What would you say are the main challenges experienced during negotiations between the responsible entity (or entities) and the plaintiff(s)?

Source: own questionnaire developed by author.

Table 12. Interview questionnaire 2 - *Claims and legal rules*

- General question**
1. Can you tell me briefly about your involvement in the efforts to reduce marine litter?
- Shipping spill mitigation**
2. What are the requirements for a shipping spill (e.g. oil, containers, chemicals) to qualify for a legal claim?
 3. In the case of a cargo ship spill, who, in your opinion, should be liable for the potential damage, and to whom? In your experience, has this been the case?
 4. In the case of a cargo ship spill, through what processes is the responsible party held into account in the North Sea?

5. What are the possible outcomes of these processes? And how is accountability being enforced on the responsible party?
6. In your opinion, are the outcomes of accountability (e.g. penalties, sanctions, monetary compensation) for the responsible party proportional to the damage they have made?
7. When monetary compensation is one of these outcomes, who, in your opinion, should assess the amount the responsible party should pay, and how do you think this amount should be calculated?
8. What would you say are the main challenges faced during cases of shipping spills?
9. What would you say are the main challenges experienced during negotiations between the responsible party and the plaintiff?
10. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the legal response and accountability processes involved in a plastic spill incident and other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?

Final question

11. Do you have any other recommendations to better protect the North Sea from plastic pollution due to cargo ship spills?

Possible additional questions

12. Do you think there should be additional measures to prevent or mitigate the damage made by cargo loss? If yes, which?
13. Would you say the responsibility in the event of a cargo loss is fairly spread? Please explain.

Source: own questionnaire developed by author.